

12 October 2010

Renée Crain
Office of Polar Programs, Division of Arctic Sciences
National Science Foundation
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Ms. Crain:

Attached is the 4th Report and Annual Program Plan of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885 between NSF and ARCUS. The report describes accomplishments for 1 January–30 June 2010 (1st 2 quarters for which we have actual budget expenditures), expected activities from 1 July–31 December 2010, and projected activities for 1 January–31 December 2011, the 4th year of this agreement. Included is:

1. A narrative summary of accomplishments (1st 2 quarters) and plans, by individual task, including relevant project appendices, a timeline of activities, and staffing plan;
2. A one-page budget summary showing costs by five major tasks: Arctic Community Science Planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, Arctic Science Education, Information and Outreach, and Core Support (Schedule A);
3. A four-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the actual costs for Year 1 and Year 2, the actual and forecast for Year 3, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for 1 January – 31 December 2011 for Year 4 (Schedule B);
4. A one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire CA by Form 1030 categories, showing the actual costs for Year 1 and Year 2, the actual and forecast for Year 3, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for 1 January – 31 December 2011 (Schedule C); and
5. The proposed budget and the request for **\$1,762,579** for the period of 1 January – 31 December 2011 on NSF Form 1030 (Schedule D).
6. In addition, we will email you an excel spreadsheet file (tab called "Excel for Renee") that indicates the funding request by the five major tasks.

The ARCUS Board of Directors and staff are very pleased with the achievements of the past year and the work we have accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF on these important efforts. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact us.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Susan Fox".

Susan E. Fox, ARCUS Executive Director and Principal Investigator

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Helen V. Wiggins".

Helen V. Wiggins, ARCUS Director of Programs and Co-Principal Investigator

**Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)
Providing Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program**

**Year 4 Program Plan and Progress Report of
Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885**

This document includes the progress report and program plan for ARCUS' five-year Cooperative Agreement, ARC-0618885, to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Division of Arctic Sciences to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education activities. This progress report and program plan summarizes, within each task and specific activity:

- Accomplishments for first two quarters for Year 3 of the Cooperative Agreement (1 January–30 June 2010);
- Remaining activities planned for last two quarters of Year 3 (1 July–31 December 2010); and
- Planned activities for Year 4 (1 January–31 December 2011).

The budget report is included at the end of this document. The narrative organizes activities into four main task categories:

1. **Arctic Community Science Planning** – coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries; includes Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and State of the Arctic Conference activities.
2. **Coordination Support for NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Programs** – specific coordination and support for the Division of Arctic Sciences programs; includes Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program Coordination, Arctic Natural Science Program Coordination, Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, and Arctic Section Science Materials.
3. **Arctic Science Education** – development and coordination of arctic-focused educational activities; includes Arctic Science Education Activities and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.
4. **Information and Outreach** – information and outreach activities; includes *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo mailing list, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Internet Media Archive, and Arctic Community Outreach.

An additional fifth category is the provision of Core Support for ARCUS' NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1. SEARCH COORDINATION

The Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) is an interagency effort to understand the nature, extent, and future development of the system-scale change presently seen in the Arctic.

The major SEARCH-related activities in the first two quarters of 2010 have been final planning and implementation of the State of the Arctic Conference and the Sea Ice Outlook; the remainder of 2010 will be focused on finalizing State of the Arctic products and initiating a strategic planning process with the SEARCH Science Steering Committee.

1.1.A. Sea Ice Outlook

Building on the success of the 2008 and 2009 Sea Ice Outlooks, the 2010 Sea Ice Outlook provided a community-wide synthesis and monthly outlook on arctic sea ice throughout summer 2010. The Sea Ice Outlook website can be found at:

<http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/index.php>.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Planning and Initiation of the 2010 Sea Ice Outlook

- Planning Meeting at State of the Arctic - A Sea Ice Outlook meeting was held on 15 March 2010 in conjunction with the State of the Arctic Conference in Miami, Florida to plan for the 2010 season. Fifteen (15) participants attended the meeting.
- Launched the 2010 Sea Ice Outlook with announcements via ArcticInfo and the SIO email list. The 2010 Sea Ice Outlook webpages can be found at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2010/june>.
- Worked with H. Eicken, J. Stroeve, and A. Tivy to edit, organize, and publish the June monthly reports, including full pan-arctic and regional reports and executive summaries. The June report is available at: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2009_outlook/report_august.php.
- Announced report via ArcticInfo, the SIO website, the SIO email list, and other relevant lists.
- Maintained the Sea Ice Outlook electronic mailing list to provide a direct means for information dissemination and communication about the SIO. There are currently 167 subscribers to the list.

- Enhanced Sea Ice Outlook search engine optimization for better ranking in Google, Bing, and other Internet search engines.

Launched and Implemented the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO)

The Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO) provides weekly walrus-relevant ice forecasts for the Northern Bering Sea and southern Chukchi Sea regions of Alaska during walrus hunting season. SIWO is a collaboration with the University of Alaska Fairbanks, the Eskimo Walrus Commission, the National Weather Service, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. The SIWO website can be found at:

<http://www.arcus.org/search/siwo>.

- Initial planning discussion at State of the Arctic Conference – Discussed initiation of the SIWO at the Sea Ice Outlook planning meeting held at the State of the Arctic Conference. Discussed timing, content, format, and distribution.
- Developed, launched, and maintained the project website, in collaboration with NOAA: <http://www.arcus.org/search/siwo>.
- Worked with G. Hufford (NWS), N. Soreide (NOAA), T. Nakamura (NOAA), and H. Eicken (UAF) to compile, edit, and publish 13 weekly reports between 2 April and 25 June.
- Announced each report via ArcticInfo and the SIO mailing list. The first ArcticInfo announcement is available at: http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi_ai_getArcticInfo/4513.
- Sent copies of the weekly reports via email and facsimile to individuals in rural communities without high-speed Internet access.
- Worked with V. Metcalf, Eskimo Walrus Commission, to increase access to SIWO for rural communities in the relevant areas of Alaska's coastline and to solicit feedback on SIWO reports.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Sea Ice Outlook:

- Continue to edit, organize, and publish the monthly reports, including full pan-arctic report, summaries, and regional report, through August.
- Write and publish an announcement of the sea ice minimum (early October).
- Develop and publish a post-season report with a retrospective analysis of the 2010 Outlook, including accuracy of estimates, seasonal dynamics, and data that can be used to improve future efforts.
- Community Meeting at AGU – An open community meeting will be held at the fall AGU Meeting to provide an opportunity for the science community to add their

perspective to what was learned from the 2010 Sea Ice Outlook, to offer suggestions for improvement for the 2011 Sea Ice Outlook, and to participate in the effort as a whole. ARCUS will lead organization of the meeting, including preparing announcements and materials, staffing, and follow-up.

- Continue website development and updates, as needed.

Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook:

- SIWO Post-Season Meeting - A small half-day meeting will be held 17 August 2010 in Anchorage, Alaska to review the 2010 season and discuss possibilities for the future.
- Discuss SIWO activities at the Sea Ice Outlook Community Meeting at AGU.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

The Sea Ice Outlook and Sea Ice for Walrus efforts are planned to continue for 2011. Specific activities will include:

- 2011 Sea Ice Outlook Reports - Work with the SIO leads, J. Overland and H. Eicken, to edit, organize, and published online monthly reports, including pan-arctic reports, regional reports, and a minimum announcement.
- Retrospective Analysis and Summary Activities – Work with J. Overland and H. Eicken to coordinate, edit, and publish online a retrospective report. Hold an open community meeting at the fall 2011 AGU to provide an opportunity for the science community to add their perspective to what was learned in 2011 and plan for any future efforts.
- Communications and Announcements – Maintain the Sea Ice Outlook online mailing list to provide a direct means for information dissemination and communication about the SIO. A subscription form is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/list.php>. Write and distribute relevant announcements to ArcticInfo.
- Website – Continue website updates and improvements, as needed.
- Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook:
 - Winter 2011 Planning Workshop - A small workshop in Barrow, Alaska will be convened to discuss plans for a 2011 SIWO with rural community members. The focus will be on increasing the project's usefulness to hunters. ARCUS will assist in agenda development and organization; no logistics support will be provided.
 - 2011 Weekly Reports - Work with G. Hufford, H. Eicken, and others to compile, edit, and publish weekly reports for the season.
 - Announce all reports via ArcticInfo and the SIO mailing list. Send copies of the weekly reports directly to communities without high-speed Internet access via

facsimile or email. Contact publications and radio stations in the relevant areas of rural Alaska to help make the information accessible to those communities.

- Website - Continue website updates and improvements, as needed.

1.1.B. SEARCH-ARCSS Understanding Change Task Force Activities

An ad hoc Task Force was convened in late 2009 to lead community activities to establish a long-term vision and provide the scientific framework of a modern effort for understanding the arctic system, with input and review from the broader community. This Task Force is a collaboration between the SEARCH and ARCSS programs. The goal of the task force is to lead development of a white paper that:

1. Identifies key unknowns and key science questions for understanding arctic system change, and
2. Identifies the next steps in synthesis activities, methodologies, mechanisms, and approaches to address the identified key science questions.

A small workshop is planned for fall 2010 to develop this white paper, which will be sent for wider community review and then finalized early 2011.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- Convened, organized, and prepared for full Task Force teleconferences monthly from early February to June and additional teleconferences with the Task Force co-chairs (John Walsh and Josh Schimel).
- Convened and organized Task Force meeting at State of the Arctic Conference in March.
- Facilitated process with Task Force members to outline, develop, and iterate a "discussion draft" of the white paper, which will be used as a starting point at the fall workshop (see initial discussion draft in Appendix A).
- Began planning for fall workshop – Secured venue; the workshop will be held in Seattle, Washington, 29 September – 1 October. Began discussions with Task Force members on potential invitees to the fall workshop.
- Developed content for and published a set of "Understanding" web pages on the SEARCH website: <http://www.arcus.org/search/understanding>.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Final planning for Understanding Arctic Change workshop, including: finalizing list of potential participants with the task force and issuing invitations; developing and finalizing workshop agenda, developing and finalizing workshop background materials and participant instructions; developing and publishing webpages for workshop.

- Finalize logistics arrangements, including all hotel and travel details.
- Convene and facilitate workshop; provide onsite logistics, organizational, and content support.
- After the workshop, work with the Task Force and workshop participants to further develop the white paper and prepare for broader community review.
- Manage community review process of white paper – announce and solicit input via ArcticInfo and other relevant mailing lists; work with the Task Force to incorporate community suggestions.
- Begin layout design for final white paper.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Work with the Task Force to finalize the Understanding Arctic Change white paper and release as final product. Final publication targeted 31 January 2011. White paper will be primarily distributed electronically, with a small in-house printing.

1.1.C. Science Steering Committee (SSC), and Panels Meetings and Support

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- Organized, planned, and convened a SEARCH SSC meeting on 15 March in conjunction with the State of the Arctic conference to discuss SEARCH activities and future plans. 22 participants attended the meeting, including SEARCH SSC members and panel chairs. Prepared meeting notes and action items, and circulated to meeting participants and NSF. Followed-up with action items, as appropriate. The meeting agenda and meeting notes are posted online on the meeting webpage at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2010/ssc/>.
- Developed memo on "Ways Forward for SEARCH," which summarizes suggestions for initiating a strategic planning process and pilot activities for SEARCH; sent memo to NSF and H. Eicken, new SSC Chair (memo is included Appendix B).
- Facilitated and organized input by the SSC to NOAA's draft "Arctic Vision and Strategy" document.
- Began compiling suggestions from SSC for new SSC members.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Work with the SSC, and NSF and other IPMC representatives to guide the SEARCH strategic planning process to develop a clear and tractable 5-year SEARCH vision.
- Schedule, organize, and convene two SSC planning teleconferences to discuss a fall

in-person SSC meeting and other SEARCH business. The first teleconference will be held on 3 August. The second will be held on 27 September.

- Plan, organize, and follow-up for a November SSC in-person meeting – The fall SSC in-person meeting is scheduled for 17-19 November 2010 in Washington, D.C. ARCUS will:
 - Provide strategic planning input for meeting goals and objectives
 - Develop draft agenda for circulation and facilitate preparation of background documents
 - Work with SSC Chair (H. Eicken), SSC members, and NSF Program Director on final agenda and background materials
 - Arrange all travel and logistics arrangements
 - Create and maintain meeting webpage and content, including agenda, participant list, and posted presentations
 - Facilitate meeting discussions on-site
 - Follow-up on all meeting action items, as appropriate
- SSC In-Person Meeting at AGU – If schedules allow, schedule, prepare, organize, and convene a SSC meeting at AGU. Work with SSC Chair (H. Eicken) on agenda and preparations.
- Support any panel activities, including organizing and planning teleconferences, development of relevant drafts and materials, website content development, and other support as needed.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Activities for 2011 will primarily depend on the outcomes of the fall 2010 SSC meeting, and will be determined in collaboration with SSC Chair and NSF Program Director. At a minimum:
 - Continue working with SSC, NSF, and other IPMC representatives to develop and finalize the SEARCH 5-year strategic vision, including recommendations for short-term SEARCH needs
 - Organize and convene SSC teleconferences, as needed
 - Organize and convene at least one (1) in-person SEARCH SSC meeting. 2011 budget includes venue and travel support for one in-person meeting.

1.1.D. SEARCH Project Catalog

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

The SEARCH Project Catalog provides an easy-to-use, online, searchable means for the SEARCH organizational structure, agencies, and scientists to discover SEARCH

implementation status and funded projects.

- Sixty (60) new projects were entered into the SEARCH Project Catalog, including Arctic Observing Network (AON), Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) and Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System (CSAS) projects.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

No additional activities planned, until after discussion at SEARCH SSC meeting in fall.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Maintain the SEARCH project catalog to enter funded SEARCH-relevant projects, as determined by the SSC.

1.1.E. AON Design and Implementation (ADI)

ADI activities are developing an overarching concept that will guide the next steps in design and implementation of the U.S. AON as part of a coordinated, international, multi-disciplinary, long-term Arctic Observing System. An ADI Task Force is exploring and evaluating different approaches and methodologies of potential use in system design. A set of ADI webpages is at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/aon/adi/>.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- In February 2010, prepared the Summary of the Arctic Observing Network (AON) Design and Implementation (ADI) Workshop that was held in December 2009 in Boulder, Colorado. The summary is posted online at:

<http://www.arcus.org/search/aon/adi/meetings/>.

- In March 2010, ADI Task Force Executive Group (Hajo Eicken and Peter Schlosser) visited with NSF and other program officers in Washington, D.C. Supported travel of Hajo Eicken to attend the meeting.

- Organized, planned, and implemented an ADI Task Force follow up and planning meeting at the State of the Arctic Conference on 17 March. Eleven participants attended the meeting. Prepared meeting notes and action items, circulated to meeting participants and NSF. The meeting agenda and notes are posted online at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/aon/adi/meetings/>.

- Helped organize, and participated in, a teleconference of the ADI Task Force, held on 23 June 2010. Prepared agenda, teleconference notes and action items, circulated to teleconference participants.
- Collected and edited summaries of presentations given at the ADI Workshop in Boulder, Colorado in December 2009.
- Developed content for and launched a set of ADI webpages: <http://www.arcus.org/search/aon/adi/>.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Help organize, and participate in, a teleconference of ADI Task Force members, to be held on 2 September 2010. Prepare teleconference notes and action items, circulate to teleconference participants.
- Schedule, prepare, organize, and convene 1-2 additional ADI teleconferences. The schedule and agenda of the teleconferences will be determined with the ADI Task Force chair.
- Work with the ADI Task Force, the SEARCH SSC, and NSF to begin planning and organizing an AON Summit meeting, to be held in 2011.
- Continue to collect and edit summaries of presentations given in the ADI Workshop in Boulder, Colorado in December 2009.
- Distribute report hardcopies from the 2009 AON/ADI meeting: "Arctic Observing Network: 2009 Status Report and Key Recommendations, Results from the Third AON Principal Investigators Meeting" and post a PDF version online.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Work with the ADI Task Force to plan and organize the Second ADI Workshop that will be held either late spring or fall 2011, possibly in Boulder, Colorado. Any logistics costs for this workshop will be included in a separate supplement request, as workshop details are not yet developed sufficiently.
 - Work with the Task Force members on developing the agenda and background materials.
 - Create and maintain meeting webpage and content.
 - Follow-up activities to the workshop. Post final materials to the website; develop and circulate workshop notes and action items; and facilitate action items that emerged from the meeting.
- Plan and organize an AON Summit meeting. Work with H. Eicken and others to develop clear workshop goals; develop agenda and background materials, create and maintain meeting webpage and content; follow-up with action items that

emerge from the meeting, as needed. Logistics costs are not expected to come through the ARCUS budget; if any logistics costs are required, they will be requested through a supplement proposal.

- By the end of year 2011, prepare and distribute the ADI final report in collaboration with the ADI Task Force chair (Hajo Eicken) and Task Force members.
- Schedule and organize implement 3-5 ADI teleconferences. The schedule and agenda of the teleconferences will be determined with the ADI Task Force chair.
- Continue to distribute the report "Arctic Observing Network: 2009 Status Report and Key Recommendations, Results from the Third AON Principal Investigators Meeting."

1.1.F. Coordination with Relevant International Efforts

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- None, other than ongoing discussions with the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) to ensure coordination between SEARCH and ISAC activities, where appropriate.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Support travel of SEARCH SSC Chair and one SSC member to meet with ArcticNet leads to discuss collaboration between the SEARCH and ArcticNet programs.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Travel for five (5) SEARCH representative(s) to international collaboration meetings; specific travel requests will be discussed with the SEARCH SSC Chair and approval requested from N. Swanberg.
- Work with SSC and coordinate with ISAC on fostering international partnerships, including an MOU with ArcticNet, and discussions with other programs (e.g., SCANNET, SAON, etc.) as appropriate.
- Partial travel for ARCUS Executive Director to Arctic Science Summit Week, Seoul, South Korea March 28 – April 1, 2011 (costs to be split between SEARCH and Core budgets).

1.1.G. Other Travel Support for SSC Chair and/or Key SEARCH Representatives

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- Supported travel of C. Lee and H. Eicken to meet with agency representatives in March 2010 in Washington, DC.
- Supported travel of H. Eicken to attend and present at the State of the Arctic Conference in March 2010 in Miami, FL.
- Supported travel of H. Eicken to attend and present at the International Polar Year (IPY) Oslo Science Symposium in June 2010 in Oslo, Norway.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Support travel of H. Eicken and L. Hamilton to visit with the NSF-OPP in August 2010 in Washington, D.C.
- Provide other travel support, if needed, to address SEARCH goals.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Provide travel support to the SSC Chair and/or key SEARCH representatives to key arctic meetings for invited SEARCH presentations and sessions, as appropriate. Budget contains funds for approximately five (5) travel slots other than the SSC meeting.

1.1.H. SEARCH Website

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- Completed ongoing website content updates, maintenance, and development.
- Completed specific content updates in "Observing Change/AON" and "Understanding Change" sections.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Continue content updates and maintenance, as needed.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Ongoing website content updates, maintenance, and development, as needed. SEARCH website will likely be restructured as a result of the strategic planning process and identification of new emerging priorities.

1.2 ARCTIC DATA COORDINATION

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Completed Report and Metadata for Arctic Observation Activities GIS Database – As proposed by ARCUS to facilitate data sharing, finished development of core metadata and report for the Geographic Information System (GIS) of U.S. observing activities that was created for the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report “Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a US Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing.” Sent metadata to CADIS and ARMAP projects.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

None planned.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

None planned.

1.3 STATE OF THE ARCTIC CONFERENCE

The State of the Arctic Conference was held 16–19 March 2010 at the Hyatt Regency Miami in Miami, Florida. The main goal of the conference was to review our understanding of the arctic system in a time of human-induced, rapid environmental change.

The State of the Arctic Conference provided an open international forum for discussion of future research directions aimed toward better understanding of the arctic system and its trajectory. Topics ranged from basic understanding of the Arctic and system-wide change, to developing response strategies to adapt and mitigate change. Major science themes included:

1. Advances in arctic system understanding - the basic functioning of the arctic system, including its human dimensions;
2. Arctic change - rapid, system-scale changes and the capability to project future

states of the arctic system under various scenarios;

3. Linkages to the Earth system - linkages and feedbacks between the arctic system and the Earth system; and
4. Translating research into solutions - informed solutions to the problems caused by environmental change.

The conference was conceived and developed by the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) and the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program communities. Other partners included: the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC), the Canadian ArcticNet Network of Centres of Excellence, the European Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES) program, and the U.S. Arctic Research Commission (USARC).

A version of the brief post-conference report/PowerPoint presentation given to NSF is included as Appendix C.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Planning for State of the Arctic commenced in 2009. 2010 accomplishments included:

1. *Developed Website* – Continual developments and updates to the website: <http://soa.arcus.org>.
2. *Internal ARCUS Planning Meetings* – Convened approximately bi-weekly internal ARCUS meetings for conference planning up to the conference date.
3. *Convened Executive Committee and Organizing Committee Teleconferences* – Scheduled, organized, created materials and agendas, and convened 10 teleconferences with members of the Executive Committee and/or Organizing Committee; planning discussions were also ongoing via email. Distributed action items and meeting summaries after each call and followed-up on action items with OC/EC members, as needed.
4. *Conference Program* – Facilitated development of the conference program by the Organizing Committee; the program included plenary sessions, parallel science sessions, and poster sessions.
5. *Community Input* – Tracked community input through an online form to collect community ideas on conference themes, topics, structure, or other suggestions relevant to the conference program. Collated and distributed input to the OC to ensure key community ideas were incorporated in conference planning.
6. *Maintained Online Registration* - Maintained an online registration form and process at: <http://soa.arcus.org/register> and a participant list, updated daily.

7. *Launched Abstract Submission* – Developed, launched, and maintained a comprehensive abstract submission and search process for poster and parallel sessions: <http://soa.arcus.org/abstracts>.
8. *Conference Outcomes and Products*: Worked with the conference Organizing Committee to develop a plan for expected outcomes and products.
9. *Speaker Recruitment and Invitations*: Worked with the Organizing Committee to recruit and invite conference speakers for plenary and parallel sessions, and provide speakers with speaker guidelines to ensure all talks adhere to high-quality content and organizational expectations.
10. *Parallel/Break-Out Session Organization*: Worked with the Organizing Committee to organize parallel or break-out science sessions, including selection of session chairs and development of session foci; work with selected session chairs to determine logistical needs; provide support to session chairs for session organization, including arranging session planning teleconferences, developing and circulating session materials, and other support as needed.
11. *Outreach and Announcements*: Distributed regular conference announcements via listserves and to key organizations and programs, with hardcopy announcements at select conferences and meetings.
12. *Press/Media Activities*: Worked with the NSF and the Organizing Committee on a media outreach strategy and onsite press coverage to ensure significant national and international media coverage and public outreach. A Miami-area consultant, with expertise in media and conference outreach, was retained.
13. *Student/Young Investigator Program*: Developed and administered a merit-based student/young investigator scholarship program to encourage the participation of young investigators, including participation of students local to the venue.
14. *Logistics*: Coordinated all logistical and technical requirements with conference center and hotels, including meeting room(s) set-up, catering, audio/visual needs, and sleeping room blocks.
15. *Travel Support*: Arranged travel support arrangements for plenary speakers.
16. *Side Meetings*: Coordinated scheduling for any associated “side meetings” requested by community groups; on-site side meeting staffing support was kept at a minimal level.
17. *Co-Sponsorship*: Solicited agency and organizational co-sponsors. 15 sponsors and partners contributed to the conference.
18. *Participant Meeting Materials*: Prepared and circulated all participant meeting

materials, including the agenda, participant list, venue and travel information, preliminary abstracts, local attraction information, and other materials. All of the materials were available as online as digital documents and on USB flashdrives at the meeting; select documents (e.g., final program, participant list) was available as hardcopy at the meeting.

19. *Presentation Planning/Support*: Worked with speakers to collect and test PowerPoints, load onto presentation computers, provide “best practice” guidance for presentations, and publish on the website (with speaker permission).
20. *On-Site Conference Staff Support*: Managed all onsite conference activities and provided staff support, including registration, speaker support, catering and audio/visual needs, web-streaming and video, plenary and parallel session management, poster sessions, press management, banquet/dinner activities, and general participant support.

The main three days of the conference included 18 plenary talks, a panel on the science-policy interface, 18 interdisciplinary parallel sessions with 160 talks, and two poster sessions with 220 posters. The fourth day focused on international collaboration and featured 21 programmatic talks, and a panel discussion. The 448 on-site participants represented 16 countries with 25% non-US., and approximately 200 additional 'virtual' participants joined via a free webcast. 64 students participated, with 26 supported in whole or part by student scholarship funds from NOAA, AOSB/IASC, and CRREL. Student activities included a Student Room, Pre-Conference Networking, Webinar, Meet and Greet Breakfast, Conversations with Scientists, Luncheon, and a Mentoring Program with 36 mentor volunteers. The conference was also covered by several print, radio, and Internet media outlets.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

1. *Conference Products*: Facilitate development and finalization of conference products, including:
 - Conference Resolution, which outlines broad priority recommendations from conference participants for future arctic science directions (led by SoA Executive Committee)
 - Meeting summary submission to *EOS* (led by Peter Schlosser and Maribeth Murray)
 - Review of key conference science highlights, submitted to a peer-reviewed journal (led by Hajo Eicken)
 - A short document summarizing societally-relevant conference science highlights for policy-makers (led by ARCUS, with Jay Gulledge and Bruce Forbes)
 - An online and DVD compilation of posters (funded by the International Study of Arctic Change)
2. *Post-Meeting Website Content/Meeting Archive*: Finalize all “archive” materials,

including the final agenda, presentation and poster abstracts, PowerPoint presentations, video, participant list, media coverage, and products, to create a comprehensive online record of the conference proceedings and outcomes.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

None.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1.1. ARCSS COORDINATION

The Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program addresses the physical, chemical, biological, and social processes of the Arctic and how these arctic systems interact with the Earth as a whole, including changes in the arctic system and their global ramifications. Since the ARCSS Committee was disbanded at the end of 2009, a minor level of ARCSS activities were planned for 2010 and are proposed for 2011.

2.1.1.A. ARCSS Seasonality Principal Investigator (PI) Meeting

ARCUS is providing logistical and travel support for a meeting of the Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System ("Seasonality") projects, scheduled for 18-19 October 2010 in Burlington, VT; as well as developing a set of webpages for the projects.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Began planning for the Seasonality PI meeting, including searching for a venue and arranging travel.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Finalize all logistics and venue arrangements, including meeting room and PI travel. No ARCUS staff will attend the meeting.
- Develop and launch a Seasonality website, in collaboration with the Seasonality PIs.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Updates to the Seasonality website, as needed.

2.1.1.B. HARC Subaward

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

None reported.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Funds remaining from 2009 at the HARC Core Office at UAF will be used by HARC to develop a final report summarizing ten years of HARC research, priorities for research (near, medium, and long-term), assessment of state of human dimensions research within arctic science, and a bibliography of HARC research publications. This document also will include a long-term vision/strategic plan to ensure continued and increased proposal pressure and to facilitate community awareness of opportunities for national, international, and interdisciplinary collaborative research and scholarly development in human dimensions research in the arctic. The report will be distributed as an online report via the HARC website and relevant mailing lists.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

None planned.

2.1.1.C. ARCSS Website

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Minor updates to the ARCSS website, as needed.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Continue updates of the ARCSS website, including development of research effort webpages, links to any ARCSS Announcements of Opportunity, lists of funded ARCSS projects, or other relevant ARCSS-specific news.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Continue updates of the ARCSS website. Specific website developments in 2011 may include transfer of the Freshwater Integration webpages to the ARCSS website, posting of final products from the SNACS projects, and updates on the SASS projects. Will also discuss with the NSF Program Director possible re-structuring of the ARCSS website to focus more on ARCSS project efforts and products, rather than programmatic content, (as was appropriate when the ARCSS Committee was active).

2.2. ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1. BERING SEA RESEARCH COORDINATION

Since March 2003, ARCUS has provided the Arctic Natural Sciences Program with organizational support and coordination of activities for the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) science planning process. BEST priorities for research were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Announcement of Opportunity (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2005/nsf05618/nsf05618.htm>) and in a special program solicitation in December 2006 (http://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf07533); awards through these opportunities were announced in July 2006 and September 2007. The funded BEST projects are the NSF contribution to a special research partnership with the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB) to support a comprehensive, vertically integrated investigation of the ecosystem of the eastern continental shelf of the Bering Sea.

2.2.1.A. Joint Science Advisory Board (SAB)

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

No activities to report in this period; the SAB did not hold any in-person meetings.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

None planned, as there is not an in-person SAB meeting scheduled for this year.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Coordinate and support travel for three (3) BEST PIs to Washington, D.C. for the 2011 meeting of the SAB (dates TBD by SAB).

2.2.1.B. PI Meeting and Support

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- ARCUS staff (B. Turner-Bogren) has participated in monthly PI teleconferences to remain abreast of program developments.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- ARCUS staff will continue to participate in monthly PI teleconferences and support any eMeetings, if requested.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- PI teleconferences and eMeetings – ARCUS staff will participate in monthly PI teleconferences to stay abreast of program developments.
- Support travel for one (1) ARCUS staff member to the annual PI meeting in 2011 to provide meeting support.

2.2.1.C. Miscellaneous Travel Support

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Provided travel support for Rodger Harvey, BEST PI, to attend the State of the Arctic Conference.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Provide travel support, if needed, to address program goals. No travel requests are pending.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Travel support to address program goals, as needed, for up to three (3) participants.

2.2.1.D HBEST Science Plan

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

No activities to report in this period.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

None planned.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Final editing and layout of the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan “*Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*,” as a parallel plan to the BEST Science Plan, if requested by NSF program director. The HBEST Science Plan seeks to initiate research to elucidate the dynamic relationship between humans and the Bering

Sea ecosystem.

2.2.1.E Bering Sea Curriculum Workshop

A Bering Sea Curriculum Workshop will be held in October 2010 in Anchorage, Alaska, to bring together teachers who had had teacher research experiences in conjunction with the Bering Sea ecosystem research projects (BEST/BSIERP) with scientists to synthesize what they had learned, turn individual K-12 lessons and activities into a greater collection of classroom resources, and help project scientists see what teachers had done with their experience. More information on the workshop, including the agenda, is included in Appendix D.

Costs for this workshop are shared between BEST/ANS, Community Outreach, and Arctic Science Education programs.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Began initial planning for workshop in collaboration with Bering Sea project PIs, the North Pacific Research Board, and COSEE (Centers for Ocean Sciences Education Excellence) Alaska, including articulating workshop goals and overall structure.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Finalize partners, partner roles, and partner contributions to the workshop.
- Finalize workshop goals and agenda.
- Finalize participant list, including teachers, scientists, project managers, a facilitator, and an evaluator.
- Facilitate and participate in the 5-day workshop in Anchorage, Alaska, which will be held 10–14 October 2010. The workshop will be evaluated through a partnership with COSEE Alaska.
- Begin development of final products from the workshop, including education lessons and resources on the Bering Sea.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Finalize curriculum products of the workshop and enter them into the online PolarTREC Learning Resources Database to develop a Bering Sea Collection of materials. The resource collection will be cross-linked to COSEE Alaska, North Pacific Research Board, and the National Science Digital Library.
- Synthesize workshop evaluation and results; develop and finalize a workshop report or white paper in early 2011.

2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES COORDINATION

The Arctic Social Sciences Program is a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary program that encompasses all social sciences research supported by NSF. The Arctic Social Sciences Program supports research that documents and analyzes the dynamic cultures, economies, and technologies of northern populations.

2.3.1.A Reprint of *Earth is Faster Now*

The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change (2002), published by ARCUS in cooperation with the Arctic Studies Center, Smithsonian Institution, and compiled and edited by Igor Krupnik and Dyanna Jolly, is a collection of ten papers describing contemporary efforts to document indigenous knowledge of environmental change in the Arctic. This text has been an extremely popular resource and is now in low supply with only a few copies left; therefore, a supplement was awarded to ARCUS to undertake a second reprint.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Worked with I. Krupnik to update the text with a new four-page preface and layout updates. Completed editing and layout for reprint and sent final document to printer.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

The reprints are expected back from the printer fall 2010.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

None planned.

2.4.1 NSF ARCTIC DIVISION SCIENCE MATERIALS

ARCUS, in collaboration with NSF program staff, will develop information and communication resources such as posters and brochures that reach across geographic, cultural, institutional, and disciplinary barriers to assist planning and integration of diverse research efforts and to improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

No activities requested in this period.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

None planned.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Work with the Renée Crain to update the *Arctic Discoveries* poster and/or Arctic Division brochure for use as an NSF outreach tool, if requested.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

ARCUS will continue to provide an educational leadership role within the arctic community through activities designed to bridge arctic science and education.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- **Extreme Cold Weather Gear Kit** – Managed requests and sent Extreme Cold Weather Gear kits for use in educating students and the public about the realities of polar research. As of 30 June 2010, kits were checked out five times to teachers across the United States. The kit was also used in conjunction with the 2010 PolarTREC Orientation and ShareFair.
- **Outdoor Days at UAF** – Trained and lent the “Carbon Travels” materials to Rebecca Legatt, a University of Alaska Fairbanks graduate student, who staffed the annual “Outdoor Days” in May 2010. Ms. Legatt recruited several additional UAF graduate students to work with hundreds of 6th grade students that participated, teaching them about the role of carbon and climate change in the arctic. The three-day outdoor education program is sponsored by the U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service and held annually in Fairbanks, Alaska.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- **Virtual Support for the Greenland, Denmark, United States Joint Science Education Tour** – Provide training and created a web-based journal, forum, and gallery on the PolarTREC website (www.polar trec.com/expeditions/greenland-education-tour-10) for 2010 NSF OPP Einstein Fellow, Marti Canipe.
- **ECW Kits** – Continue loaning ECW kits, as requested.
- **IPY E-Meeting Follow-up** – Provide limited staff time for transfer of information, processes, and recommendations resulting from the IPY Education and Outreach Project E-Meeting held in fall 2009.
- **2010 AGU Fall Conference** – Provide partial travel support for one ARCUS staff and

one teacher to attend the AGU fall conference to coordinate and participate in arctic education activities and sessions, including the AGU Exploration Station and APECS Career Development Workshop.

- **AGU Exploration Station** – Provide minor support for promotional materials and shipping of resources for an arctic and climate change educational booth at the fourth annual AGU Exploration Station, a public outreach activity that will be conducted on Sunday, 12 December 2010, prior to the AGU Fall Meeting. The event, coordinated by the NASA Solar Dynamics Observatory's Education and Public Outreach department, is free and open to members of the San Francisco public to come and learn and explore geophysical sciences with agencies and organizations attending the conference.
- **APECS Early Career Workshop at AGU** – Provide minimal support and meeting space in the ARCUS Community Meeting Room on Sunday, 12 December 2010 for a Career Development Workshop being co-organized by the Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) and the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS). The workshop will primarily focus on developing skills not often taught during graduate education programs, including developing key messages about research projects, communicating research to various audiences, and effective expressions and outreach methods in proposal writing.
- **Other** – Other activities, as appropriate and as funding allows. Partial funding for the Bering Sea Curriculum Workshop will be taken from the Arctic Community Outreach Budget.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- **Outdoor Days 2011** – Participate in Outdoor Days 2011 (May 2011). Present a global climate change/arctic related activity and organize the event onsite.
- **Greenland Education Tour Support** – Provide support, as determined by NSF (i.e. website, training, online journal and photo gallery, live event, etc.).
- **SACNAS National Conference** – Travel for one staff and one additional student or scientist to attend the 2011 SACNAS National Conference in San Jose, California 27-30 October 2010. ARCUS will host an exhibit hall booth to share arctic science with nearly 2,000 participants of the meeting, and will additionally participate in other education and mentoring related activities as available.
- **2011 AGU Fall Conference** – Provide support for one ARCUS staff and two teachers to attend the AGU fall conference to coordinate and participate in arctic education activities and sessions, including the AGU Exploration Station.
- **AGU Exploration Station** – Provide staff support and minor materials/shipping costs for an arctic and climate change educational booth at the annual AGU Exploration Station, a public outreach activity conducted prior to the AGU Fall

Meeting. The event is free and open to members of the San Francisco public to come and learn and explore geophysical sciences with agencies and organizations attending the conference.

- **Extreme Cold Weather (ECW) Gear Kit** – Continue mailing ECW kits to teachers and the public as requested.
- **Monthly Early Career Scientist Professional Development Webinars** – Held in conjunction with the APECS Education and Outreach Committee, facilitate monthly webinars for early career scientists and educators (web seminars), which will feature mentors from the science and education communities sharing topics which may include, how to develop an effective poster, how to present to public audiences, forging connections with schools, strategies for broader impacts, working with community leaders, turning science to action, etc. All events can be archived and available online.
- **Polar Education Mailing List** – Maintain the ARCUS Polar Education List, which provides a venue for educators, researchers, and learners to exchange information about opportunities, challenges, methods, resources, important events, and other useful topics. The list is moderated but participatory so subscribers may post information or respond to posts.
- **Other** – Other arctic science education and outreach activities, to be determined with the program officer, as opportunities arise and funding allows.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents (see website at: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/index.html).

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- Supported Orville Huntington to travel to Illinois to discuss climate change and its effects in Alaska, and indigenous knowledge. Orville spoke to 175 third grade students, 25 undergraduate students, and 100 of the Charleston general public while in Illinois. His lectures received attention from the local press. See more on the tour at: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/2010_tours.html.
- Supported Allen Marquette to travel to Valdez, Alaska to lecture on Alaska during the Pleistocene epoch. Allen conducted six school lectures that included 200 elementary students and 40 junior high students; an evening public lecture; and met

with community members and teachers to help organize a kid's science club modeled after a program in his community of Cordova. See more on the tour here: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/2010_tours.html.

- Supported David Klein to travel to Louisiana to lecture on arctic ecology as it relates to climate change, as well as lessons learned from the 1989 Exxon Valdez incident in Alaska. The visit attracted significant press coverage. David spoke to 60 middle school students, addressed participants of the "Adult Learning Program," conducted an Arctic Educator Training for teachers, and a public lecture comparing Antarctica and the Arctic. See more on the tour here: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/2010_tours.html.
- Published several speaker profiles online to the Speakers Bureau.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Continue current program, with support for AVS tours as applications are received, up to four (4) more tours.
- Send a call via ArcticInfo for AVS host applications.
- Update the AVS flyer and send to places of interest, including school districts, museums, community centers, and science centers, with an introductory letter inviting applications.
- Continue to add new speaker's profile to the online Speakers Bureau as appropriate.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Continue current program, with support for approximately eight (8) speakers.
- Update speaker's bureau with new photos and bios, as appropriate.
- Continue to send updated AVS flyers to communities of interest and distribute at various meetings.
- Additional outreach activities, including a call for researchers to join the Speakers Bureau.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public.

4.1 *Witness the Arctic* Newsletter

Witness the Arctic is a newsletter that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications. To improve timeliness of reporting and reduce printing and mailing costs, *Witness the Arctic* has changed to an online format, with more frequent issues. A small number of hardcopies are printed in-house to send to key community members, to distribute at meetings, or as requested.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- **Completed Spring 2010 Issue** – Finalized and released spring 2010 issue (Volume 13, Number 4). The feature story was on the State of the Arctic conference, and included several articles on arctic logistics, SEARCH, arctic natural sciences, and international and other news. The issue is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic>.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- **Complete Fall 2010 Issue** – Write, edit, and publish the fall issue, in collaboration with contributing authors.
- **Complete 2010 End-of-Year Issue** – Write, edit, and publish the end-of-year issue in December, collaboration with contributing authors.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Continue development and publication of at least three (3) online issues of *Witness the Arctic*.
- Continue to develop web pages and interface for an increasing dynamic, database-driven, and searchable content.

4.2 Website and Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves several thousand pages and files. The website is the focal point for educational programs, various community science planning efforts, and provides important information and resources to the research community about research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. The website provides program information; electronic copies of publications; agendas, abstracts, and participant lists from meetings, the online calendar, and other resources.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

The website has had 108,657 page views since 1 January 2010.

- **Overall Website Improvements**
 - Continued moving "static content" into a system that allows for more dynamic functionality (Drupal content management framework).
 - Continued to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality. Increasingly used website-tracking software to analyze website use patterns, using Google analytics, and increased use of dynamic content.
- **Updated and Maintained the Online Arctic Calendar** – The online calendar provides an up-to-date and comprehensive calendar of arctic meetings and conferences: <http://calendar.arcus.org/>. Calendar events were added as they became available through ArcticInfo, the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), or through other lists. The International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) was contacted to gain more international contributions to the Arctic Calendar; members of the IASC executive committee now forward upcoming international events.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Continue website updates and developments, with a specific focus on direct program needs.

- Continue porting static content into the Drupal content management framework.
- Continue to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality. Increasingly used website-tracking software to analyze website use patterns, using Google analytics, and increased use of dynamic content.
- Improve meeting abstract submission functionality.

- Update list management software.
- Continue posting events to the online calendar.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Continue to develop/improve website, with a focus on increasing dynamic content, as appropriate for specific CA projects and programs.

- Continue to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality.
- Finalize porting static content into the Drupal content management framework.
- Continue to add upcoming events relevant to the arctic community to the Arctic Calendar.

4.3 ArcticInfo Mailing List

ARCUS continues to develop and maintain ArcticInfo, the primary electronic mailing list for the arctic research community. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other news. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website.

Submissions and subscribers to ArcticInfo have increased steadily over the past year and has required increasing staff support. In 2009, ARCUS changed ArcticInfo's format to include more than one message in an email, to reduce the number of emails and to reduce the amount of time an announcement waited in the message queue.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Continued to develop and maintain the mailing list, including receiving, editing, and posting 314 announcements to the list between 1 January and 30 June 2010. There are currently 6,667 email subscribers.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Continue to develop and maintain the mailing list, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements.
- Update the ArcticInfo webpage with additional information regarding announcement submissions, including specifics on what will and will not be posted as well as details on what type of information should be submitted based on announcement type (job posting, meeting, etc.).

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Continue to develop and maintain the moderated mailing list, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements to the list.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to facilitate networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the Directory, which includes information on over 4,000 U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions (see website at: <http://www.arcus.org/researcher/index.html>).

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Continued to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers, which currently contains 4,129 individual entries. Completed the annual update of directory information.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Send ArcticInfo announcement inviting new submissions to the Directory.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Continue to update and maintain the Directory annually.

4.5 Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of polar-relevant photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are shared through the ARCUS website at: <http://media.arcus.org>.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

- 24 videos were made publicly available, including 23 from the State of the Arctic Conference.
- 1314 photos were made publicly available.
- Created a "Featured Collection" on the Internet Media Archive's home page showcased photos from the State of the Arctic Conference.
- The Internet Media Archive had over 13,000 page views.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- Continue to add photos, videos, and other media files.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- Continue to add photos, videos, and other media files.
- Migrate the Internet Media Archive to a new gallery system with improved search capability.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS continues to conduct a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

No activities were planned for this period.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

- **2010 AAAS Arctic Science Conference** – Provide travel support for ARCUS staff to attend the 2010 AAAS Conference in Anchorage, Alaska, to present and share information on SEARCH, State of the Arctic, and other ARCUS Cooperative Agreement activities.
- **Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall 2010 Meeting** - Provide and organize a “Community Meeting Space” at the Fall 2010 AGU Meeting to encourage scientific collaboration and to make face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community.
- **Other** – Other community outreach activities, as needed and as funding allows. Partial funding for the Bering Sea Curriculum Workshop will be taken from the Arctic Community Outreach Budget.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

- **Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall 2011 Meeting** – Provide and organize a “Community Meeting Space” at the Fall 2011 AGU Meeting.
- **Development of "Trade Show" Materials to Promote Arctic Science** – Develop a suite of materials including exhibit booth signage and related handouts to promote

arctic science, arctic science careers, arctic education materials, and other resources for members of the general public, undergraduate and graduate students, and for use at science conferences.

- **Other Community Outreach** – Outreach at AGU and other prominent arctic or related meetings and conferences, as appropriate.

4.7. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) International Polar Year (IPY) Report

Mike van Woert, OPP Executive Officer, had requested that ARCUS assist with the completion of a special issue of Arctic Research of the U.S. (published by the NSF for the IARPC and the Arctic Research Commission) on the International Polar Year.

NSF put this project on hold. No planned activities unless NSF requests further work on this report.

5.1 CORE SUPPORT

Core Support includes program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects and cannot be attributed to a specific project.

Accomplishments for 1 Jan–30 June 2010 (Year 3)

Continued support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

Remaining Activities for 1 July–31 Dec 2010 (Year 3)

Continue Core Support of CA activities; staff time, however, will be allocated to direct projects as much as possible.

Proposed Activities for Year 4 (2011)

Continue support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries. Core support budget includes funds for Executive Director and Director of Program travel to NSF to continue collaborative planning for CA programs.

Understanding Arctic Change White Paper

INTERNAL "DISCUSSION" DRAFT

Version: 15 September 2010

This document was developed by Understanding Change Task Force members as a beginning discussion draft for the workshop. This is not a comprehensive draft of the white paper, but rather initial ideas for key points.

The comments shown in the right margin (in blue) are those of task force members from a review of an earlier draft among the Task Force members.

Guiding Principles and Introduction:

- Strategies for "Understanding Arctic Change" need to be system-focused, going beyond narrow disciplinary boundaries or priorities;
- A forward-thinking strategy must embrace the human dimension of arctic change by developing socially-relevant science questions;
- The "intersections" between arctic system components are important. By focusing on these intersections as the targets, it allows us to draw in many diverse specific elements of the arctic system and move away from questions such as 'how does arctic change affect my particular disciplinary area?'
- We need to think beyond traditional methods of science planning and implementation to nurture transformative research.

We propose five overarching questions that can focus the planning for the next phase of Understanding Arctic Change science.

We conceptually divide these into three groups. The first two questions focus on the nature and predictability of the arctic system. The third and fourth questions focus on interfaces between components of the arctic system and between the arctic and global system. The last is a single question focusing on changes in the cryosphere—we target the cryosphere because it is the element of the arctic system that sets it apart from other components of the earth system, and because many system changes are driven directly by changes in the cryosphere.

Under each science question we also provide the following:

1. Brief description
2. Examples of sub-questions
3. Goals for science questions
4. Approaches to meet goals—recommendations for mechanisms, community activities, modeling, synthesis activities, meetings, workshops, etc.
5. Partnerships and coordination required (multi-agency cooperation between specific agencies, or bringing in certain expertise/communities, or collaboration between programs, etc).

1. How Can Predictions of the Arctic System Facilitate Planning and Adaptation at Different Timescales?

This section/question drafted by: John Walsh (With Terry Chapin)

Brief Description

Meeting the needs of planners, policymakers, business, and communities challenged with developing and implementing strategies for adapting to and mitigating arctic change requires useful predictability over various timescales. This requires determination of (1) what planners and decision-makers need, (2) the actual predictability of the arctic system, and (3) factors affecting the implementation of plans. The challenge is then to make optimal use of the intersection of user requirements and scientific feasibility to achieve the desired accuracy and predictability, which in turn requires that any potential predictability be realized. Some features of the arctic system are more predictable than others.

Example Sub-Questions

What is the predictability of the drivers of arctic change over seasonal to decadal timescales?

How can predictability of the drivers of arctic change be transferred to predictions of broader environmental changes affecting ecosystems and humans?

What do users, planners, policymakers, and other arctic stakeholders require in order that predictions be useful?

What aspects of the predictability of the arctic system are sufficient to be useful to planners and policymakers?

How can useful aspects of potential predictability best be realized?

What are the optimal ways for conveying predictive information, given the uncertainties that will be inherent in predictions?

How can predictive information best be utilized by arctic stakeholders?

Goals

The primary goals are to quantify the predictability of arctic variability and change and capitalize upon this predictability in ways that are most useful to stakeholders. Given the complex group of users and their varying timeframes of interest, a prerequisite is to identify user needs and requirements for effectively incorporating predictions of arctic

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:36 PM

Comment: Not sure what this means.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:36 PM

Comment: There is an important addition and difference and potentially a trade off between knowability, accuracy, predictability and local relevance to practitioners' decisions (decision-makers have been documented to prefer local relevance over accuracy or predictability!). You may want to consider this further in the remainder of this section - I didn't make comments in every place where the word predictability is mentioned. But some of the sub questions may be revised in light of this comment..

change into proactive responses to change. An additional goal is to synthesize information on the natural variability that lies at the core of any assessment of predictability.

Approaches

Climate models and other approaches (statistical, paleo) have the potential to contribute to evaluations of arctic variability and change, which must be quantified in order to establish potential predictability. Assessments of predictability of arctic change must include considerations of changes in the physical drivers (greenhouse gases, aerosols, etc.) as well as social and economic drivers that will affect the arctic environment. Partnerships with the global climate modeling community will facilitate progress in assessing predictability of the physical drivers of arctic change, but it will also be necessary to draw upon broader system modeling that includes a human component.

Partnerships and Coordination Required

Partnerships with the global modeling and paleoclimate communities will be required for progress in assessments of arctic predictability. National centers such as NCAR, GFDL and GISS are examples of potential partners in climate modeling. International activities such as the Climate and Cryosphere Program (CliC, within the World Climate Research Program) have also targeted arctic predictability as a priority, so international synergies are likely to emerge. International coordination of different national activities will be necessary, as will coordination across U. S. agencies (NSF, NOAA, DOE, NASA) with ongoing and emerging programs in predictability. Finally, interactions between the natural and social sciences will be necessary for assessing user needs, determining “useful” predictability, and fostering optimal uses of the predictive information by stakeholders. Human impacts on the trajectory of the arctic system will also be an essential consideration, requiring further collaboration between the physical and social science communities.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:37 PM

Comment: Maybe point to another of the 5 major questions here?

2. What are Arctic System Tipping Points and Abrupt Changes That Are/Will Be Most Consequential for Ecosystems and Humans?

This section/question drafted by: Andi Lloyd and Terry Chapin

Brief Description

“Tipping points” and abrupt changes represent thresholds in the arctic system, across which large magnitude changes may occur rapidly. These thresholds may be physical or chemical thresholds (e.g., the melting temperature of ice, the threshold saturation state for aragonite), may arise because of internal feedback processes (e.g., positive feedbacks promoting shrub expansion), or may reflect an interaction between the two. Tipping points represent a particular category of abrupt change: points in time at which small changes in conditions produce large, potentially irreversible changes in a system. The key thresholds of the arctic system are poorly understood at present and are in need of quantitative assessment; this will inevitably involve considerations of feedbacks. The assessment of tipping points and abrupt changes should focus on the changes most consequential for

Helen Wiggins 9/14/10 9:51 AM

Comment: What about the concept of tipping elements, which is a larger scale version of this concept? See Lenton et al. 2008 PNAS paper

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:44 PM

Comment: What about ecological or social tipping points? And the interaction between the geophysical/chemical ones and the ecological and social ones? - tipping points may be reached sooner or later due to this interaction.

ecosystems and humans, but it is not presently known which tipping points and abrupt changes fall into this category.

Example Sub-Questions

What are the role of extreme events as triggers for abrupt changes and tipping points? How important is their role compared to relatively small, incremental changes?

What are the most consequential thresholds in the arctic system, and how irreversible are the changes that will occur across those thresholds? Which thresholds represent points at which change is practically irreversible (on the span of human lifetimes) even if changes in external drivers cease?

Do thresholds (and to what extent) in the physical arctic system (sea ice, atmosphere, permafrost) trigger tipping points or abrupt changes in arctic ecosystems?

Can changes (and to what extent) in biophysical systems trigger abrupt changes in social systems (e.g., transportation, industries, ability of certain human land uses)? How do human actions or reactions feedback to the biophysical system?

How might positive feedbacks drive ecosystems across tipping points? What are the mechanisms driving rapid change in terrestrial and marine ecosystems?

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:45 PM

Comment: Why? Of course everything influences ecosystems. I like ecosystems. But it's probably also useful to explore purely physical tipping points and abrupt change. Although "purely physical" they can still be quite complex and involve many interdisciplinary aspects of the climate system. EG, Wally Broecker's Great Lakes flushing events that "hose" the North Atlantic Ocean and "turn off" the Gulf Stream. Or Lindsay and Zhang's study showing that a strong wind event can flush sea ice out of the Arctic Ocean, and in concert with a warming climate, makes renewed growth of thick ice unlikely.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:46 PM

Comment: Is this a contradiction to your definition of a tipping point? (defined as leading to irreversible changes)

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:46 PM

Comment: Too vague – be specific or drop

Goals

The primary goal is to identify the key thresholds in the arctic system, and to highlight those thresholds that represent true tipping points, i.e., across which change is effectively irreversible. A secondary goal is to quantify the factors most important in moving the system across those thresholds—an analysis of the role of extreme events may be particularly crucial here. A third goal is to better understand how threshold events and resulting changes impact ecological and social systems Building capacity for better collaboration across disciplines (particularly between terrestrial and marine scientists) will be crucial for making progress.

Approaches

Achieving these goals will require the integration of models, long-term, sustained observations, and experimental manipulations. Integration with the paleoecological and paleoclimatic community as well as the ecological and various social sciences would be necessary for addressing questions about long-term system dynamics and the feedbacks within them.

Partnerships and Coordination Required

Partnerships between the modeling community, networks of long-term observing sites (including AON, NEON, and LTER networks), and the paleoclimate community are essential, as are connections between marine and terrestrial and social science research communities. Given the emphasis on nonlinear systems dynamics, it would be advisable to build partnerships with research institutes that explore complex systems dynamics and nonlinearity.

3. How Will the Critical Intersections Between Human and Natural Systems in the Arctic Change Over the Next Several Decades?

This section/question drafted by: Josh Schimel

Brief Description

Interfaces are often critical zones in their own right, but are also frequently the most sensitive points in any system. They are “thin” relative to the core systems and sensitive to large inputs of material and information. A beach, for example, has high property value, but can be swept away in a single storm. They also act as filters, controlling the information and material that passes between systems. Frequently, however, disciplinary approaches minimize their focus on these interfaces; to use the beach example again, terrestrial ecologists see beaches as part of the ocean while oceanographers see them as part of the land, while social scientists may see them as part of economic, land use, recreational systems or hazardous zones of human-environment interactions. When evaluating the interactions among multiple systems, it is therefore vital to understand the interfaces: What influences pass through them? How sensitive are they to changes in either core system?

One set of critical interfaces in the arctic system are those between the human and natural components. We need to understand how they interact and how those interactions may will change over the next decades.

Addressing intersections between natural and human systems demands organizing research that understands each system independently but is also able to explore the special and synergistic dynamics occurring at the interface so that a better, interdisciplinary understanding of the whole can be developed.

Example Sub-Questions

What are the critical intersections between human and natural systems in the Arctic?

How will climate change influence physical and ecosystem properties in regions of special interest to residential, commercial, and human enterprise?

How will industrial activity in the Arctic change in response to altered climate and thermal regimes?

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:46 PM

Comment: This seems like a purely Human Dimensions initiative. That's fine, but perhaps it could be broadened to include non-human-focused research on "intersections?"

How will changing patterns of development impact arctic environmental systems and feedbacks to the climate system?

How will changing patterns of climate and marine activity (e.g., fishing, shipping, mineral extraction) alter marine food webs and fishing productivity in the Arctic?

Goals

The primary goals of this research are to identify the key interfaces where human and natural systems interact with each other, the drivers on these interfaces, how they will change over time, and how changes in the interface will influence the different core systems.

Approaches

Currently, most research in the natural sciences focuses on the core functioning of systems. This provides considerable information on the factors driving change in the interfaces. Understanding human systems has lagged behind; most such research in the Arctic has focused on indigenous communities, rather than on large-scale industrial activity that may be important in driving large-scale change.

We therefore need three types of research: 1) domain-based research that focuses on the interfaces; for example models of ocean circulation that target understanding water and material exchange through the nearshore zone, or how economic development alters the surface properties of the Arctic that impact the climate; 2) research that explores how changes in the interfaces alter functioning of the core systems; and 3) research that puts this together across the interface—integrative studies that explore the feedbacks between human and natural systems and how the interfaces respond to and mediate those feedbacks.

Partnerships and Coordination Required

Productive partnerships are required between groups who will integrate across the natural-human system boundary. We need to develop stronger connections to economists, industrial planners, engineers, and others whose expertise targets industrial and development activities. We also need to develop stronger linkages between researchers and people who live and work within the Arctic to integrate human responses and feedbacks more effectively into our models of how the arctic system works.

4. What Are the Critical Intersections Between the Arctic System and the Global System?

This section/question drafted by: Scott Elliot and Susi Moser

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:10 PM

Comment: I think the core/interface distinction may be a bit artificial and maybe overwrought. It's a very mechanistic way to distinguish two parts of a system that may not be so easily or clearly separated. I mean, where, for example, would the core of the "human system" called "a coastal fishing community" be, and where its interface, and where the respective parallel core of the "Coastal/marine ecosystem"? Gets pretty tricky. I would tone that distinction down in the rest of this section...

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:58 PM

Comment: Shorten these sub-sections to make consistent with others

Brief Description

Arctic issues must be understood in a global context. Lower latitude processes are coupled to the arctic system at all levels—geophysical, geochemical, ecological, social, and political. Examples are readily enumerated. The ocean transports heat energy and critical materials such as nutrients into the central Arctic basin. Both water ice and greenhouse-gas-containing clathrate deposits may be destabilized as a result of warming, while ecosystems may shift geographically, resulting in potential ecosystem reorganization. Atmospheric carbon dioxide is responsible for not only the bulk of global warming but also the rapid acidification of arctic seawater. The extent to which the Arctic Ocean can take up carbon dioxide has global implications, and further determines cloud properties and the fate of air pollutants. Atmospheric and riverine inputs to terrestrial ecosystems influence atmospheric composition, humidity, carbon cycling, and permafrost degradation. Meanwhile there are feedbacks that affect the middle latitudes and the global scale, through ice, snow, aerosol, cloud and vegetation reflectivities and greenhouse gases. In addition, changes in both arctic terrestrial and marine ecosystems are critically connected with species and ecosystems elsewhere via the migration of species. Such changes can link in important ways to public health concerns (e.g., the migration of disease vectors, the deeper penetration of diseases into regions previously too cold to provide habitat or transfer opportunities). Local human concerns include changes in the hydrological cycle (since they affect water resources), transportation on or through sea ice, and a variety of national and human security issues. The Arctic and northern seas support the planet's richest fisheries, supplying a major fraction of global protein, yet future resource extraction has the potential for ecosystem degradation and/or reorganization through trawling activities. Transportation through the Northeast and Northwest passages may have significant global economic, trade, and security implications, as well as the potential as a vector for invasive species to the marine ecosystem. Mineral extraction from areas currently still covered by sea ice are already fostering international tension among Arctic nations regarding claims of sovereignty, economic influence, and competition. Such novel national and international geopolitical and policy challenges and changes associated with nations competing to corral energy, transport and defense resources in remote areas will impact local economic opportunities, challenges, and risks. In turn, local human concerns will need to percolate upward to national and international bodies if they require supra-local institutions and influence to be addressed adequately.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:58 PM

Comment: Positive, negative and copious feedbacks?

Example Sub-Questions

What are the major geophysical and chemical feedback loops through arctic and global climate? Consider all the potential geophysical and biochemical connections, including energy to ice, cloud to ice, biogeochemistry to cloud, biogeochemistry to ice, terrestrial and marine ecology to radiation, terrestrial and marine processes to atmospheric composition, environmental chemistry to habitability, and all major and trace elemental cycles.

What is the nature of major biogeochemical processes and ecological feedback loops

through arctic and global climate? This question takes the physical/chemical changes identified above and links them to large-scale (regional to global) ecological processes and interactions.

How will changes in the biota react to and perhaps even drive arctic climate change? This question must be addressed for all individual ecozones at a succession of latitudes including those outside the Arctic. Quantification of the effects must also be extended to the level of the ecological province and biome.

How do human social, cultural, economic, and (geo)political systems interact with the above and vice versa? The need is for precision and quantification, using a variety of approaches, as appropriate (scenario analysis, modeling, case studies, expert elicitation etc.). Key areas of interest are impacts on arctic public health, economic development, and cultural change. Changes in land and marine use in the Arctic will be driven by global economic and energy or defense/national security needs. Risks associated with a warming Arctic (transition from a wilderness/scientific laboratory/homeland for native peoples into a battleground for human cultural and economic competition) must be assessed to usefully inform preemptive policies.

How can the arctic research enterprise be kept nimble and flexible to respond to rapidly emerging questions and challenges in an environment where the pace of regional change is so rapid?

How do the crossing of arctic tipping points reverberate globally (and nationally in the respective countries), and vice versa? Inherently related to this question is the level of global stabilization needed to achieve a reasonable level of regional (arctic) stabilization allowing the arctic region to provide sufficient ecosystem services and quality of life for its people. This maps (at least partially) on the question of what constitutes “dangerous interference with the climate system?” (UNFCCC Article 2). It has long been recognized that globally aggregated measures of “danger” or “reasons for concern” hide regional variation in the degree to which impacts manifest. The Arctic will likely experience “dangerous” impacts sooner than other regions. Research on this topic would basically result in substantive information regarding regional impacts that may be judged as “dangerous”.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:26 PM

Comment: Needs further discussion and elaboration – perhaps question should not be subsumed here, but be considered a main overarching question

Goals

The questions raised here overlap in various ways with those raised under the other key questions. Such overlap is useful, as enhanced understanding will come by way of linking separate areas of inquiry. Our goal given the rapidity of arctic change is to predict the details of mutual shifts in polar and global systems. The generated knowledge must be relevant for policy- and decision-makers at various relevant political levels (local to international).¹ Quantitative understanding must be achieved and disseminated in such a

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 1:59 PM

Comment: I think this is too big a goal, and unrealistic. Given the countless factorial interactions in the system, prediction is the wrong word (should be project), and simulation exercises or scenario exercises should NOT be eliminated, as they are - BY FAR - the more realistic goal that can be achieved.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:08 PM

Comment: I'm not sure what this means. Be more specific.

¹ This notion of prioritizing research that both advances fundamental knowledge and answers decision-makers' questions (“use-inspired research”) has been proposed as a guiding principle by the America’s Climate Choices Science panel report (2010).

way that the public, stakeholders and policy makers can all enter into informed decision making processes. This requires ongoing and frequent interaction between researchers (the web of interactions must include all the disciplines mentioned above) and the ultimate users of the information produced.

Approach

Meeting these goals demands a strongly motivated and organized research strategy cutting across institutions, disciplines, and institutional cultures (which vary by discipline, and between researchers and decision-makers). Here motivation means that given the urgency of the arctic situation, funding cycles should be fast, flexible, and driven by real time constants of the arctic system. Regarding organization, hierarchies of field and laboratory study must be designed to address the highest priority unknowns and then to feed process and distributed models. For some questions, the ultimate tool for manipulating the generated information is systems modeling, and again a hierarchy of approaches is needed. In other instances, quantitative systems modeling is inappropriate or impossible, yet significant advances in understanding can be achieved through creative and complementary use of other methodologies, including non-quantitative qualitative research. In either case, the strata of effort must combine detail and geography. Local low dimensionality, Pan-Arctic and global scale codes must all interact effectively. Note that several groups world-wide have recently begun to consider the prospects for true Arctic Systems Modeling. Their experiences can be drawn upon.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:08 PM

Comment: A fast cycle means that grants are of short duration.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:08 PM

Comment: Unclear what this means

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:09 PM

Comment: Unclear; too jargony.

Paradoxically, in the context of a very rapidly changing climate, researchers from different disciplines will need to learn each other's language, approaches, and methodologies. Experience suggests this takes deliberate attention, persistence, and precious time. Building research teams with "standing power" over time reduces this cost of learning for future projects. Including researchers well experienced in interdisciplinary collaboration also helps this ongoing learning and integration process.

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:09 PM

Comment: Unclear

Partnerships and Coordination

The task of simulating the arctic system in isolation is far beyond the capabilities of any single research group. We must include planetary scale couplings and collaboration. Thus teaming across groups, institutions, countries, and continents will be necessary. It may be that traditional PI-driven university science must be adjusted in this research because of its unique combination of size and urgency. Interactive regional-global system perturbations will require larger-than-traditional collaborative efforts, and great skill in project management. Template programs should be investigated in which this type of structure has been achieved. When tenable frameworks are identified, they should be used as models for the true organizational structure.

Concluding Thoughts

Across the history of environmental and social science, it has often been the case that unknown circuits through a regional or global system turn out to be critical to their fate. Not surprisingly, physical and social teleconnections are of increasing interest in various scientific disciplines. Examples include human and non-human population dynamics and the northern fisheries, chlorofluorocarbons and their relation to polar stratospheric ozone, the greenhouse system itself, as well as interactions in the increasingly globalizing economic system. The Arctic may at some point be viewed as a fragile system to be protected from such surprises. This fourth topical area proposes to seek or anticipated these interconnections in a systematic fashion. *[could be moved as an opening framing statement, too.]*

5. How Will Changes in the Cryosphere Drive Changes in Other Components of the Arctic System: Economic, Social, and Environmental?

This section/question drafted by: Regine Hock and Hajo Eicken

Helen Wiggins 9/7/10 2:09 PM

Comment: This seems very similar to Question 3.

Brief Description

Shrinking sea ice extent, retreating glaciers, thawing permafrost, and changes in snow distribution are the most visible indicators of arctic warming and are among the strongest drivers of other changes. Yet our understanding of the economic, social, and environmental consequences of cryospheric change is lacking. Assessment of these consequences will require credible projections of the cryospheric changes as well as the development of impacts models that entrain the broader environmental and social sciences.

Example Sub-Questions

What are the spatial and temporal patterns and trends of cryospheric change? How are the components of the cryosphere (terrestrial and marine permafrost, sea ice, glaciers and ice sheets, seasonal snow) coupled to each other and to other components of the arctic system?

What are likely future changes and related uncertainties?

What are the ongoing and future effects of cryospheric changes on landscape evolution, hydrology, sea level, marine and terrestrial ecosystems, infrastructure and human activities?

How can the cryosphere be better integrated into arctic and global system models?

Are any of the cryospheric changes practically irreversible and if so, how might this impact the evolution of the arctic system? What is the role of cryospheric feedbacks in driving arctic and global system-wide change?

Goals

The main goal is to quantify current changes in the arctic cryosphere, project future

changes, and assess their environmental, social, and economic impacts on a decadal to century time scale. From this goal follows an evaluation of the importance of feedbacks and irreversible (within the context projected future change) transitions in driving system-wide changes in the Arctic. Two major uncertainties, the fate of perennial sea ice in the Arctic and the contribution of the Greenland and smaller ice sheets to decadal and centennial-scale sea-level rise, need to be evaluated and quantified to reduce uncertainties in projections for other components of the arctic system.

Approaches

Remote sensing and in situ observations must be continued to monitor ongoing cryospheric changes and place them in historical context. Methods need to be refined to resolve the discrepancies between existing data products, such as sea ice extent based on different satellite passive microwave algorithms. Improvements are needed in data management and methods must be developed to reduce uncertainty in changes on cryospheric variables for which data are sparse (e.g., permafrost temperature). Coupled cryospheric system models need to be further developed, including models that address prediction of changes on sub-decadal down to seasonal timescales. Impact models must be developed that include relevant cryospheric processes. These requirements require involvement of national and international modeling groups, possibly through existing working groups or by building on model intercomparison programs.

Paleo-data may help unravel past responses of the cryosphere to changes in forcing and their impact on the arctic and global system. Complex systems theory may shed light on plausible trajectories of the cryosphere as it undergoes substantial change. Workshops such as American Geophysical Union (AGU) 's Chapman conferences or similar high-profile exploratory meetings may be required to engage contributions within and outside of the arctic community.

Partnerships and Coordination Required

More unified approaches in studying the interaction and coupling between cryosphere components require coordination between the different branches of cryospheric science and with related disciplines such as climate modeling, oceanography and hydrology. International programs (such as CliC) as well as working groups such as the AGU Cryosphere Focus group can help. Furthermore, the paleo-climate and complex systems community will have to be engaged to examine fundamental questions of system-wide cryospheric change. This will require new partnerships. Assessing the impacts on human activities and ecosystems require strong partnerships with mission agencies in the U.S. and a dialog with the social sciences.

Ways Forward for SEARCH

To: Neil Swanberg, Simon Stephenson, and Renée Crain (NSF), Hajo Eicken (SEARCH SSC Chair), Peter Schlosser (Past SSC Chair)

From: Helen Wiggins and Susan Fox (ARCUS)

This memo summarizes ways forward for SEARCH through two new activities: (1) commencement of a Strategic Planning Process and (2) launch of a Pilot Project(s) to test new models of SEARCH implementation and collaboration. Through implementation of these activities, SEARCH will be well positioned to succeed its promise as an innovative and cross-cutting scientific program.

I. SEARCH Status and Successes: Where We Are Now

SEARCH is a unique interdisciplinary and multi-agency program that has developed significantly over the past several years. It is now a well-recognized program with many successes:

- SEARCH can boast a large and diverse community of arctic scientists who support the SEARCH program. The scientific capacity of SEARCH is impressive.
- A myriad of reports summarizing SEARCH scientific priorities has emerged from the SEARCH community (see Appendix A, "SEARCH Development Timeline").
- The Observing component of SEARCH thrives, with over 50 projects funded through NSF's Arctic Observing Network (AON) and additional contributions from other agencies. The AON Design and Implementation (ADI) process will facilitate a well-designed Arctic Observing System.
- SEARCH has convened the Understanding Arctic Change Task Force to develop a long-term vision for understanding the arctic system, which will significantly advance SEARCH's "Understanding Change" component.
- SEARCH activities have developed and fostered collaborations with several national and international arctic programs (ARCSS, DAMOCLES, etc.)
- The Sea Ice Outlook demonstrates the capacity of SEARCH to create innovative community science projects that not only advance scientific knowledge, but also serve stakeholders and the public.

II. SEARCH Challenges and Needs

As a complex, multi-agency program that addresses pan-arctic interdisciplinary arctic change, SEARCH faces inherent challenges that more "traditional" disciplinary or thematic programs do

Appendix B. SEARCH Strategic Planning Memo

not face. It is neither easy nor straightforward to plan and implement a cutting-edge effort like SEARCH. As such, SEARCH needs to:

1. Move forward quickly to take advantage of emerging opportunities – We are at a stage in SEARCH where we can take advantage of emerging opportunities and community energy, and respond to urgent information needs of rapid arctic change. SEARCH should also demonstrate its ability and willingness to test new models of programmatic implementation. The results of OPERA place the impetus on SEARCH to move forward on key SEARCH issues that require a rapid response, but with a strategically planned approach.

2. Define a clear long-term vision, goals, and measures of success – To build on the successes thus far and to move strategically to the next stage, we must have clear, defined, and tractable vision and goals. Without this, SEARCH runs the risk of using resources on activities that are ad-hoc, uncoordinated, and at best result in only incremental progress, without significant evolution towards a common vision.

3. Adopt an action plan to enact the vision and goals – To make SEARCH vision and goals a reality, we must develop a clear implementation and action plan that charts a path for the next several years. This plan would define appropriate structures, processes, activities, and milestones.

We have the capacity and energy to move forward—we just need a clear path to do so. Thus, to address these needs, we see two approaches:

1. Embark on Strategic Planning Process – Undertake a collaborative strategic planning process to produce a clear SEARCH vision (e.g., "SEARCH 2015") and a supporting action plan to realize that vision.

2. Launch a Pilot Project – Develop and launch a small pilot project(s), focused on a specific theme(s) or science question(s), to test activities towards innovative SEARCH implementation.

The strategic planning and pilot project activities would be done concurrently with active SEARCH efforts, including AON/ADI, the Understanding Arctic Change Task Force, the Sea Ice Outlook, and SEARCH data management (if a data project is funded through OPERA).

III. Way Forward #1: Strategic Planning

The Benefits of Strategic Planning

Strategic planning energizes and moves an organization or program toward its mission and goals. It:

- Clarifies purpose and vision.
- Paints a picture of where the organization will go, the anticipated outcomes, and how to get there.
- Provides a guide to focus and prioritize time, people, and resources in running a successful effort.

"I skate to where the puck is going to be, not where it has been." – Wayne Gretzky

Appendix B. SEARCH Strategic Planning Memo

- Engages diverse stakeholders and results in products that help to recruit partners and participants.

Strategic planning is critical to the success of any organization or complex project (Mintzberg 2005). With distributed collaborative efforts such as SEARCH, careful planning, communication, and clarity of roles becomes even more important (Olson et al. 2008).

Indeed, a formal planning process is essential for significant progress. Positive and high-impact innovation in an organization occurs when changes are intentional (i.e., planned) and strategic (see Figure 1, below).

Figure 1. Adapted from Palmer and Kaplan, 2007. Strategically planned changes—whether incremental or transformative—produce benefits for an organization.

Our goal here is to introduce a process that moves SEARCH forward and allows us to anticipate and manage subsequent change. These changes may be minor or major, but they would occur in a constructive context, especially important when maturing a complex collaborative program such as SEARCH.

Strategic Planning in a SEARCH Context

The strategic planning process proposed here would be designed to fit SEARCH's unique needs. In addition to standard planning best practices (e.g. setting clear goals, setting timeline and milestones, process for assessing progress, etc.), we must consider several issues specific to SEARCH:

- The community will need to clarify and document what SEARCH *is* - as its role as an umbrella structure to coordinate sets of projects, as a funding source to implement new scientific priorities, and/or as a structure and process that can synthesize ongoing research.

Appendix B. SEARCH Strategic Planning Memo

- SEARCH must *prioritize* goals, objectives, and activities. Because the program is so broad, we cannot do everything at once nor please all communities at all times.
- SEARCH must be nimble, adaptive to changing science priorities, and able to take advantage of emerging opportunities. We need to develop a mechanism for revising plans as necessary.
- We will need to define clear roles and responsibilities for all SEARCH entities, including the Science Steering Committee (SSC), Panels, Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC), and the Science Management Office, and consider changes to current structures. Updating the Terms of Reference would be part of this process.
- SEARCH strategic planning should incorporate a combination of "top-down" (i.e., programmatic vision and funding from agencies) and "bottom-up" (i.e., scientific vision and energy from the community). SEARCH cannot succeed without "top-to-bottom" processes that move together toward a cohesive vision. A traditional model of funding individual projects or efforts is not sufficient without coordination and cohesive planning.
- We will need to draw from several different literatures, including: strategic planning, organizational management, collaboratories/virtual organizations, SEARCH science planning (i.e., existing SEARCH documents), and emerging scientific priorities (e.g., as identified in SoA). We would essentially marry planning practices from the corporate and organizational literature with the SEARCH scientific context.
- The strategic planning process should include diverse perspectives from internal and external communities, including:
 - SEARCH *leadership* – SSC, panels, and IPMC.
 - Successful *international* arctic programs.
 - Successful *interdisciplinary* programs.
 - Successful U.S. *interagency* science programs.
 - *Broader arctic science community*, including projects and programs that may be 'components' of SEARCH (BEST/BSIERP, etc.).
 - *Outside experts*, including those in strategic planning for science programs or associations, visionaries in Collaboratory or Virtual Organization development, etc.
 - SEARCH *stakeholders* – decision-makers, representatives from northern communities, etc. —those who will use the science.
- We will need to design an assessment process that includes annual review of measurable goals, and planning that is tied to annual budgeting processes.

IV. Way Forward #2: SEARCH Pilot Project(s)

A fundamental challenge in SEARCH is that its broad focus makes it difficult to enact large-scale innovative developments. A solution to this is to begin testing new approaches through pilot project(s). Smaller-scale pilot projects would allow us to test new models for planning and

Appendix B. SEARCH Strategic Planning Memo

implementation (e.g., collaboratory concepts, cross-project and cross-agency coordination, etc.). A pilot project could be developed quickly, and would allow us to be adaptive without risking large amounts of resources. It would focus on a *tractable* science theme or question.

For example, the SEARCH SSC, with input from the IPMC, could select a priority theme or topic that is ready for a creative pilot effort (e.g. 'changing arctic sea ice', 'changing permafrost', etc.). We would first assess what current relevant activities and projects were already underway on which to build. We would define strategic goals and products over short-term (1–2 year) time frame, focusing on interdisciplinary and cross-cutting activities. We would then define and implement a plan for meeting the project goals (including required staffing, roles of SSC, Panels, agencies, and specific activities), and include formative evaluation activities to assess and refine progress throughout the project.

V. Immediate Next Steps

Again, both the strategic planning process and pilot projects would be done concurrently with current SEARCH activities—it is important to build on our current successes and maintain momentum.

The immediate next step is for the SEARCH leadership to provide feedback on the ideas summarized within this memo. Do these ideas resonate with you? Do they represent a direction you'd like to see SEARCH go?

If so, these ideas would be presented to the SSC for discussion; if the SSC supported this direction, we would aim to start planning in earnest this fall. An example timeline of how activities might be phased is presented in Appendix B.

List of Appendices:

Appendix A: SEARCH Development Timeline

Appendix B: Example Timeline and Phasing

Appendix C: Selected References

State of the Arctic Conference

16–19 March 2010
Miami, Florida, USA
soa.arcus.org

Summary Report & Data

Conference Goal & Focus

- **Main Conference Goal:** Review our understanding of the arctic system in a time of rapid environmental and socio-economic change.
- **Four Major Science Themes:**
 1. Advances in arctic system understanding
 2. Arctic change
 3. Linkages to the Earth system
 4. Translating research into solutions

Structure

- 4-day conference: 3 days for main program and 1 day focused on “International Collaboration”
- Main Program
 - 18 plenary talks plus panel
 - 18 interdisciplinary parallel sessions with 160 talks
 - 2 poster sessions with 220 posters
- International Day
 - 21 international program talks plus panel

Attendance

- 448 Participants (with ≈200 additional joining via webcast)
- 16 Countries Represented; 25% Non-US

Participants By Country

By Organization Type

Student Participation

- 64 Students Total (Defined as undergraduates, graduate students, or those who graduated within the past year)
- 26 Supported (in whole or part) by student scholarship funds from NOAA, AOSB/IASC, and CRREL
- Activities Included:
 - Student Room
 - Pre-Conference Networking Webinar
 - Meet and Greet Breakfast
 - Conversations with Scientists Luncheon
 - Mentoring Program (36 Mentor Volunteers)
 - “Effectively Communicating Climate Change” Workshop

Press

- Covered by several print, radio, TV, and Internet media
 - “Five Feet of Seawater to Flood Florida’s Coastline Over the Next 100 Years, Scientists Warn”, *The Palm Beach Post*
 - 5 Interviews on National Public Radio Affiliates and Radio News Stations
 - 2 T.V. spots on NBC affiliates
 - Internet Coverage: NBC online, others

Participant Evaluation

- 31% Response Rate
- 78% rate conference 4 or 5 (out of 5) for "offering opportunities for presenting and sharing arctic science in an interdisciplinary manner"
- 83% rate conference 4 or 5 for "meeting expectations for providing a means to network with colleagues both formally and informally"
- 76% rate conference plenary sessions 4 or 5 for quality and variety
- 81% rate conference web site 4 or 5 for quality and satisfaction

Sample of Participant Comments

- In the past 9 months as director, Navy Task Force on Climate Change, I've attended dozens of climate and arctic-related conferences. This conference had the combination of the highest participant energy, quality of research and breadth of participation I have seen. Outstanding conference -- it was a joy to speak at. Thank you!
- I have never attended such a well run and organized event...I can honestly say that this conference was amongst the best experiences of my young academic career
- This was a huge hit and in recent days I've had several discussions, comments from students and also emails highlighting how badly we needed this and what a great job was done by all
- Flawless operation at the meeting
- The entire conference was well-planned and executed, something the entire community has grown accustomed to with ARCUS! this conference reinforced and highlighted the importance of integrated, inter-disciplinary Arctic research
- The meeting in Miami was great and I am so glad I was able to attend - learned alot and made good contacts...
- This venue featured a great lineup of plenary speakers and a truly interdisciplinary focus - live streaming added value, reach, and impact. Congratulations and thanks!
- Congratulations again on a job well done- last week was really, really fabulous!!!

Critiques

- More natural science/ecology and social science
- More arctic peoples / indigenous representation
- More time for posters
- Higher international participation a challenge, especially with competing meetings and declining travel budgets
- Too much cheese 😊

Take-Home Points

From Peter Schlosser and Hajo Eicken, Organizing Committee Members

- Acceptance that **anthropogenic change** is overprinted on natural variability
- Arctic system science is being conducted in the context of a **changing Arctic** and, where appropriate, in the context of global change
- Arctic science community is increasingly **interdisciplinary** and framing their research around topics and themes rather than traditional disciplines
- **Societal need and solution-oriented research** is becoming central for new research programs in the Arctic
- Community now exploring questions on adaptation to and mitigation of arctic change in **innovative ways that may lead the way for other regions** (because of strong partnerships with indigenous organizations, government and non-government entities, and the private sector)
- The **need for stakeholder involvement** into the early phases of the design of research programs is becoming more apparent and accepted
- Opportunities and challenges to switch to **new research modes** that would allow multi-domain system-scale observations of the arctic system simultaneously with interpretation of new data streams and synthesis/modeling

Expected Products

Target for Completion: Fall 2010

1. Conference statement/resolution
2. Conference summary
3. EOS article on conference outcomes
4. Policy paper (to peer-reviewed journal)
5. Synthesis paper (to peer-reviewed journal)
6. Special volumes from parallel sessions (to be determined by session chairs)
7. Variety of archival materials: plenary and parallel session presentations, presentation and poster abstracts, digital copies of posters, video of plenary talks, final attendee list, photos

**Thank You to the SoA
Sponsors and Participants!**

Appendix D. Bering Sea Ecosystem Professional Development Workshop

Introduction and Goals

ARCUS is proposing to partner with the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB) and COSEE Alaska to provide a five-day professional development workshop involving teachers and scientists. The workshop would be held in Anchorage, Alaska, October 11-15, 2010.

The participants would include 15 teachers who have been involved with the BEST-BSIERP project (through PolarTREC, NOAA Teacher-at-Sea, or ARMADA) and community teachers from the five communities involved in the study (Savoonga, Togiak, St. Paul, Emmonak and Akutan). In addition, five BEST-BSIERP researchers will also attend for the entire week.

The goals of the workshop are:

1. To increase the teachers' content knowledge about marine and climate change research in region, specifically related to the hypotheses and results of the BEST/BSIERP ecosystem study.
2. To improve the knowledge and skills related to best practices for K-12 science education for both teacher and scientist participants.
3. To increase the contributions of scientists to the broader impacts of their research.
4. To complete a consolidated group of lesson plans and a listing of related multi-media resources aligned with state and national science standards and ocean and climate literacy principles, which would be posted online and archived in ARCUS' online Learning Resource Database and shared through the national COSEE network and NPRB website as well as in the communities along the Bering Sea.

Justification

Over the course of about 5 years, there have been a number of teachers that have participated in research experiences in the Bering Sea. As part of their research experience program requirements, the teachers have created several lessons related to the Bering Sea ecosystem but to date, the lessons haven't been formalized into something that could be used by teachers in the region and/or in the larger education community. In addition, the lessons don't include the more recent data that was collected and/or analyzed data. There is a growing need by teachers to include and have access to data that can be brought back to the classroom.

Outside of the lesson plans, there is also a need to establish contact and collaborations between teachers and others, particularly when working with the small communities along the Bering Sea. This workshop gives a face to everyone and allows us to formulize those connections and give resources back to the communities as well as teachers that teach in the Bering Sea communities.

Workshop Activities and Products

The workshop design and flow is based on workshops conducted by COSEE and uses their best practices for professional development. We will be drafting the agenda with the facilitator in upcoming weeks, but in general, the workshop will focus on the following tasks:

- Introduce the goals and outcomes to participants
- Share already created lessons and materials and examine the gaps in this area
- Expand teacher participants' knowledge about Bering Sea science
- Expand researcher participants' knowledge and best practices and effectiveness related to K-12 science education
- Refine and expand lessons and materials to include State and National Science Content Standards as well as Climate Change and Ocean Literacy Standards.
- Create new material where needed to fill in the gaps
- Pull lessons and materials together for a cohesive body of work related to this ecosystem

Partners

There are several partners involved in the workshop. Below is a short paragraph about their contributions.

COSEE-Alaska

- Contribute \$15K to pay for teacher stipends (\$500 each) and for teacher substitute costs (\$500 each).
- In-Kind contribution of evaluator to conduct the evaluation component of the workshop. Includes pre-workshop assessment and post-workshop report to be shared with partners.
- In-Kind contribution for COSEE-Alaska Program Manager to help with the workshop.
- In-Kind contribution for to finalize the lesson plans for dissemination and share with COSEE network educators.

North Pacific Research Board

- In-Kind contribution of meeting space in Anchorage, Alaska, which includes the use of their videoconference equipment.
- In-Kind contribution of a contractor to conduct a resource search related to Bering Sea prior to the workshop.

- Contribute \$20K to pay for researcher travel (airfare, per diem, lodging) to participate in the workshop as well as the travel of the facilitator and evaluator. In addition, they will cover other workshop costs (e.g. catering, meeting supplies, etc...) as needed.
- In-Kind contributions of staff to assist and present during the workshop.

ARCUS

- Contribute \$20K from CA to pay for (15) teachers to travel (airfare, per diem, lodging) and two staff members to attend the workshop. Funds will also cover staff time to attend and prepare for the workshop.
- In-Kind contribution to assist in dissemination of final product across networks as well as posting to Learning Resources database that is part of the PolarTREC website.

Other Partners

NOAA Teacher at Sea will probably contribute some funds to supplement teacher travel. Amount to TBD as it depends on the number of alumni that attend the workshop. They will also have researchers that will attend the workshop and/or present via videoconference. ARMADA project also had two teachers that will probably attend the workshop. Depending on their remaining funding, they might be able to contribute toward the teachers travel to attend. The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service as well as various Universities have several researchers that are willing to attend the workshop for a day or two and/or participate via video-conferencing to help deliver content to the participants.

Facilitator

The facilitator for the workshop, Dr. George Matsumoto, will be paid for through his affiliation, The Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute, to facilitate the workshop. The partners will cover his travel costs to/from Alaska. Dr. Matsumoto is the Senior Education and Research Specialist at the Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (www.mbari.org/education). Dr. Matsumoto also developed the Education and Research: Testing Hypotheses (EARTH) program and facilitates workshops at MBARI to bring educators, scientists, and engineers together to develop effective educational practices for access and use of near-real-time data (www.mbari.org/earth/). The EARTH workshops involve collaborative work by the scientists and educators and result in online educational materials. He has served on the Centers for Ocean Science Education and Excellence (COSEE) National Advisory Board since 2003 and recently served on the National Academies Committee to review NOAA Education.

Evaluation

An evaluator working with COSEE-Alaska will evaluate the workshop. There will be a pre-workshop and post-workshop follow-up and will evaluate both the teacher and researcher participants. The evaluation will follow a recent meta-analysis study of teacher professional development conducted by the Council of Chief State School

Officers (CCSSO) and the effects of quality professional development on improving student achievement that was recently documented in their report, *Effects of Teacher Professional Development on Gains in Student Achievement: How Meta Analysis Provides Scientific Evidence Useful to Education Leaders* (2009).

The assessment of scientist participants with educators will focus on understanding the impact of the interaction on 1) subsequent professional efforts, 2) quality and durability of relationships that derive from such interactions, and 3) interest in and willingness of both parties to introduce traditional ecological knowledge and place-based understandings within the research and teaching endeavors.

Specifically for scientists the survey will assess the nature and type of engagement with the educators, how such engagement sustains, what impact it has on either their scientific research or Broader Impacts requirements, and what roles and relationships they have with COSEE Alaska, *NPRB and ARCUS*. For educators similar questions will be addressed in addition to questions about changes in knowledge, attitudes and capacities to teach others about ocean science research and how traditional ecological perspectives are considered.

DRAFT

Bering Sea Ecosystem Professional Development Workshop
10-14 October 2010
Anchorage, Alaska

Project Goals & Desired Outcomes

Our goal is to bring together teachers who have been at sea with BEST-BSIERP project researchers, as well as community teachers from the five communities involved in the study (Savoonga, Togiak, St. Paul, Emmonak and Akutan), and other teachers from Bering Sea/Aleutian Islands and Bering Straits region, to interact with each other and project scientists and create a cohesive body of work from their individual activity sets, blogs, journals, videos, and educational resources related to this historic ecosystem study.

Saturday, 9 October 2010

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>Technology Needs</i>
All Day	Participants Travel to Anchorage	All Participants	
Afternoon	Workshop Setup at NPRB	All Project Team Members	

Participants travel Saturday, 9 October. Check in at the Captain Cook Hotel.

Sunday, 10 October 2010

Participants: Make sure to bring your laptop computer with you throughout the workshop.

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>Technology Needs</i>
11:00 - 12:00 PM	Brunch (Provided)	All Participants	
Introduction and Overview			
12:00 – 1:00 PM	Introduction & Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participant Introductions - Agenda for week - Workshop goals - Housekeeping items 	Janet Warburton, ARCUS	None
1:00 – 1:30 PM	Opening Remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who are we? - What brought these groups together? - What are the desired outcomes of the workshop? 	Nora Deans, NPRB	None
1:30 – 2:00 PM	Icebreaker Activity	George Matsumoto, Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute	None
2:00 – 3:00 PM	Overview of Existing Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results of Bering Sea learning resources literature review conducted by NPRB 	Nora Deans, NPRB	None
3:00 – 3:15 PM	Break		
3:15 – 3:30 PM	Introduction to the Lesson Plan Template	Kristin Timm, ARCUS	None

3:30 – 4:00 PM	Standards Overview - National Science Standards - Alaska State Standards - Ocean & Climate Literacy Standards	Marilyn Sigman, COSEE Alaska	None
4:00 – 4:45 PM	Group Discussion - What are your needs and expectations?	George Matsumoto, Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute	None
4:45 – 5:00 PM	Evaluation		
5:00 PM	Adjourn		
5:30 PM	Meet to walk to XXXXXXXX for Mixer and Dinner		
5:30 – 6:30 PM	Opening Mixer	All Participants	
6:30 PM	Group Dinner: Location	All Participants	

Monday, 11 October 2010

Participants: Bring materials for presenting your classroom activity, lesson, or demonstration, including presentation slides if applicable.

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>Technology Needs</i>
7:00 – 8:00 AM	Breakfast (Provided)	All Participants	
8:00 – 8:20 AM	Introduction & Welcome - Plan of the Day - Introduction of new participants - Housekeeping items	Janet Warburton, ARCUS	None
Teacher & Science Content Presentations			
8:20 – 9:20 AM	Teacher Presentations: (4) ¹ Deanna Wheeler – <i>Lesson Name</i> Simone Welch – <i>Plankton Parade</i> Maggie Prevenas – <i>Lesson Name</i> Tonia Kushin – <i>Lesson Name</i>		Videoconference Out
9:20 – 9:30 AM	Break		
9:30 – 10:15 AM	Science Presentation: Bering Sea Ecosystem Study - Big Picture Overview	Mike Sigler, NOAA Alaska Fisheries Science Center & Rodger Harvey, University of Maryland	Presenting Via Videoconference
10:15 – 10:25 AM	Break		
10:25 – 11:15 PM	Group Discussion:	All Participants	Discussion Via

¹ Teacher presentations will be 10 minutes with 5 minutes for transition and questions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bering Sea as a system - Climate induced change - Why location matters 		Videoconference
11:15 – 12:00 PM	Teacher Presentations: (3) Samantha Dassler-Barlow - <i>A Bering Sea Food Web</i> Jillian Worssam - <i>Bering Sea to AZ: Microscopic Plants and Animals</i> Teacher Name – Lesson Name		Videoconference Out
12:00 – 1:00 PM	Lunch (Provided)	All Participants	
1:00 – 1:30 PM	Science Presentation: Plankton Ecology and Biogeochemistry	Ray Sambrotto, Columbia University	Presenting in-person, Videoconference Out
1:30 – 2:00 PM	Science Presentation: Benthos	Emily Davenport, University of Georgia at Athens	Presenting in-person, Videoconference Out
2:00 – 2:45 PM	Group Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower trophic levels - Plankton and phytoplankton - Benthic organisms 	All Participants	Discussion Via Videoconference
2:45 – 3:00 PM	Break		
3:00 – 3:30 PM	Teacher Presentations (2) Teacher Name – Lesson Name Teacher Name – Lesson Name		Videoconference Out
3:30 – 4:00 PM	Science Presentation: Higher Trophic Levels	Francis Wiese, NPRB	Presenting in-person, Videoconference Out
4:00 – 4:30 PM	Science Presentation: Higher Trophic		

Levels

4:30 – 5:15 PM	Group Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Seabirds- Marine mammals	All Participants	Discussion Via Videoconference
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5:15– 5:30 PM Evaluation

5:30 PM Adjourn

5:30 – 7:00 PM **Opening Reception** with hors d’oeuvres All Participants

7:00 PM **Dinner:** On Own

Tuesday, 12 October 2010

Participants: Bring materials for presenting your classroom activity, lesson, or demonstration, including presentation slides if applicable.

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>Technology Needs</i>
7:00 – 8:00 AM	Breakfast (Provided)	All Participants	
8:00 – 8:15 AM	Introduction & Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan of the Day - Introduction to new participants - Housekeeping items 	Janet Warburton, ARCUS	None
Teacher Presentations			
8:15 – 9:00 AM	Teacher Presentations (3) Teacher Name – <i>Lesson Name</i> Teacher Name – <i>Lesson Name</i> Teacher Name – <i>Lesson Name</i>		Teachers Presenting Via Videoconference
9:00 – 9:10 AM	Break		
Science Content Presentations			
9:10 – 9:40 AM	Science Presentation: Sea Ice and Biological Communities	Rolf Gradinger, University of Alaska Fairbanks	Presenting Via Videoconference
9:40 – 10:20 AM	Group Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seasonal Sea Ice - Ice Algae 	All Participants	Discussion Via Videoconference
10:20 – 10:30 AM	Break		
10:30 – 11:10 AM	Science Presentation: Ocean Circulation, mixing, etc.	Tom Weingartner, University of Alaska	Presenting Via Videoconference

11:10 – 12:00 PM	Group Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ocean currents - Stratification and circulation - Oceanography of the Bering Sea 	Fairbanks All Participants	Discussion Via Videoconference
12:00 – 1:00 PM	Lunch (Provided)	All Participants	
1:00 – 1:40 PM	Science Presentation: Modeling & Climate	Nick Bond, University of Washington	Presenting in-person, Videoconference Out
1:40 – 2:20 PM	Group Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What can modeling tell us - Climate predictions - Future scenarios for the system 	All Participants	Discussion Via Videoconference
2:20 – 2:40 PM	Evaluation		
2:40 – 3:00 PM	Break and regroup at 3:00 PM for walk to Anchorage Museum	All Participants	
3:15 – 6:00 PM	Field Trip: Anchorage Museum <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Museum Exhibits - Tour of Arctic Studies Center Gallery - Educational Opportunities at the Museum 	Aron Crowell & Monica Garcia, Anchorage Museum	
6:00 PM	Group Dinner: Location		

Wednesday, 13 October 2010

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>Technology Needs</i>
7:00 – 8:00 AM	Breakfast (Provided)	All Participants	
8:00 – 8:15 AM	Introduction & Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan of the Day - Introduction to new participants - Housekeeping items 	Janet Warburton, ARCUS	None
Science Content Presentations			
8:15 – 8:45 AM	Science Presentation: Human Dimensions	Henry Huntington, Huntington Consulting	Presenting in-person, Videoconference Out
8:45 – 9:30 AM	Group Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commercial fisheries - Subsistence use - Local and traditional knowledge - Relationships between a changing marine environment and Bering Sea communities 	All Participants	Discussion Via Videoconference
9:30 – 9:45 AM	Break		
Learning Resource Planning & Development			
9:45 – 10:00 AM	Review of Lesson Plan Template	Kristin Timm, ARCUS	None
10:00 – 11:00 AM	Forming Groups and Picking Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review Major Questions of the Study - Review of Topics Presented - Matrix of Learning Resources - Form work groups 	All Participants	None

Small Group Work			
11:00 – 12:00 PM	Small Group Work - As individual or small groups, work on projects	All Participants	None
12:00 – 1:00 PM	Lunch (Provided)	All Participants	
1:00 – 4:45	Small Group Work - As individual or small groups, work on projects - Break food available as needed	All Participants	None
4:45 – 5:00 PM	Evaluation		
5:00 PM	Working Dinner: Pizza		
5:00 PM – ?	Small Group Work - As individual or small groups, work on projects	All Participants	None

Thursday, 14 October 2010

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Who</i>	<i>Technology Needs</i>
7:00 – 8:00 AM	Breakfast (Provided)		
8:00 – 8:15 AM	Introduction & Welcome - Plan of the Day - Introduction to new participants - Housekeeping items	Janet Warburton, ARCUS	None
Small Group Work			
8:15 – 11:00 AM	Small Group Work - As individual or small groups, work on projects - Break food available as needed	All Participants	None
11:00 – 11:30 AM	Learning Resources - Next Steps - Review Process - Where they will live	Kristin Timm, ARCUS	None
11:30 – 1:00 PM	Lunch (Provided)	All Participants	
<i>During lunch, participants should upload final lesson plans in templates to FTP site and prepare for afternoon presentations.</i>			
1:00 – 2:00 PM	Teacher Presentations²	All Participants	Video Conference Out
2:00 – 2:30 PM	Wrap Up Discussion	All Participants	
2:30 – 2:45 PM	Evaluation		
2:45 PM	Adjourn		

² Teacher presentations will be about 20-30 minutes per group or individual.

Major Milestones and Activities for 2011

ARCUS Cooperative Agreement Year 4 (2011) Tentative Staffing Plan: By hours/FTE

Staffing plan is tentative and subject to personnel changes, changes in CA activities, and other staffing decisions.

Staff, Position	1.1	1.2	1.3 SoA	2.1.	2.2.1	2.3.	2.4.1 Arctic	3.1 Arctic	3.2 Arctic	4.1	4.2 Website	4.3	4.4 Directory	4.5	4.6 Arctic	5. Core
	SEARCH	Arctic Data		ARCSS	Bering Sea Research	Arctic Social Sciences	Section Materials	Science Education	Visiting Speakers	Witness the Arctic		Arctic Info	of Arctic Researchers	Internet Media Archive	Community Outreach	Support
Susan Fox, Executive Director	200	0	0	20	25	10	20	10	10	60	100	5	20	20	200	600
Ada Bower, Business Manager	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Helen Wiggins, Director of Programs	850	0	0	100	80	0	10	25	20	200	100	5	20	30	200	250
Reija Shnorro, Project Manager	1000	0	0	200	40	0	0	100	80	0	0	10	0	0	200	60
Kristina Creek, Executive Assistant	200	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	90	0	750	70	0	200	0
Zeb Polly, System Administrator	40	0	0	0	0	0	90	0	0	0	100	0	0	15	0	1055
Ronnie Owens, Web Developer	10	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	40	0	1800	0	10	20	20	0
Janet Warburton, Project Manager	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Kristin Timm, Project Manager	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	5
Joed Polly, Media/Video Manager	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1200	25	5
Judy Fahnestock, Project Assistant	200	0	0	150	0	0	0	200	0	0	400	0	150	0	150	5
Charlotte Rill, Accountant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Julie Griswold, Project Manager	500	0	0	20	20	0	0	200	450	0	0	50	40	20	40	120
Betsy Turner-Bogren, Project Manager	180	0	0	0	400	0	0	200	0	1000	0	200	20	0	0	5
Jonathan Pundsack, Project Manager	1675	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	300	0	0	0	0	0	5
Debra Laroe, Project Assistant	300	0	0	0	20	0	0	50	160	0	0	0	80	40	60	40
Total Hours	5165	0	0	610	595	10	120	785	760	1650	2500	1020	410	1345	1135	2165
Equivalent Total FTE Per Activity	2.48	0.00	0.00	0.29	0.29	0.00	0.06	0.38	0.37	0.79	1.20	0.49	0.20	0.65	0.55	1.04

Summary of Proposed Funding 10/12/10 9:43	2008 9-month year) TOTAL	2009 YEAR 2	2010 - YEAR 3 ACTUAL & FORECAST	2010 - YEAR 3 BALANCE REMAINING	2011 YEAR 4
	ACTUAL	ACTUAL			
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 SEARCH Coordination	206,572	270,309	417,091	34,156	443,708
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination	10,196	12,778	-	-	-
1.3 State of the Arctic	-	203,436	470,607	(34,156)	-
Subtotal Direct Costs	216,768	486,523	887,698	-	443,708
Indirect Costs	82,398	168,918	365,872	0	182,719
	299,166	655,441	1,253,570	0	626,427
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION					
2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination					
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination	143,922	72,845	68,894	5,848	28,589
2.2 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination				-	-
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination	12,801	24,995	50,703	(0)	56,328
2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination				-	-
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination	-	-	5,848	(5,848)	-
2.4 Arctic Section Science Materials				-	-
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	-	1,000	3,983	-	8,063
Subtotal Direct Costs	156,723	98,840	129,428	(0)	92,980
Indirect Costs	21,117	17,192	53,618	(0)	38,289
	177,840	116,032	183,046	(0)	131,269
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	24,763	17,277	21,466	-	46,261
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	5,454	18,009	26,630	-	45,473
Subtotal Direct Costs	30,217	35,286	48,096	-	91,734
Indirect Costs	11,482	12,649	19,965	-	37,777
	41,699	47,935	68,061	-	129,511
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH					
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	36,861	78,305	59,411	0	88,594
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	108,974	65,535	109,480	-	122,875
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver	14,334	30,906	26,925	0	36,098
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	1,002	6,780	7,995	-	12,859
4.5 Internet Media Archive	7,087	29,196	38,614	(0)	46,887
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach	235,776	61,637	53,828	-	102,047
Subtotal Direct Costs	404,034	272,360	296,253	(0)	409,359
Indirect Costs	153,533	97,417	121,996	(0)	168,574
	557,567	369,776	418,249	(0)	577,932
5. CORE SUPPORT					
5.1 Core Support	231,553	184,066	181,635	0	210,679
Subtotal Direct Costs	231,553	184,066	181,635	0	210,679
Indirect Costs	87,990	69,945	74,797	-	86,758
	319,543	254,011	256,433	0	297,436
Total Direct Costs	1,039,408	1,077,076	1,543,111	0	1,248,461
Total Indirect Costs	356,406	366,121	636,249	(0)	514,116
TOTAL	1,395,815	1,443,197	2,179,355	(0)	1,762,579
	NSF CA-approved	2,026,742		Yr 4 Budget	1,762,579
	NSF supplement	203,747		Balance YR 3	0
	Adj to Education	(16,634)		FUNDING REQUEST	1,762,579
	Reprogram to 09	(34,500)			
	2010 BUDGET	2,179,355			

ATTACHMENT A

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.								
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009 - YEAR 2	2010	2010	2010	2010	2010	2011
	year)							
	TOTAL	ACTUAL	BUDGET	AS OF 06/30/10	JULY-DEC	& FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET
I. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING								
1.1 SEARCH Coordination								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	79,569	177,144	184,703	61,500	123,203	184,703	-	266,229
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	22,219	22,429	27,090	2,544	24,546	27,090	-	23,000
Participant Support Costs	54,964	45,903	187,259	10,057	143,046	153,103	34,156	119,479
Materials and Supplies	161	-	1,100	-	1,100	1,100	-	500
Publications/Dissemination	3,153	1,201	4,875	(554)	5,429	4,875	-	1,500
Consulting	3,050	5,550	1,500	700	800	1,500	-	-
Computer Services	2,578	2,378	2,000	1,478	522	2,000	-	1,000
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	40,878	15,704	42,720	5,839	36,881	42,720	-	32,000
Total direct costs	206,572	270,309	451,247	81,564	335,527	417,091	34,156	443,708
Total indirect costs	78,524	95,118	186,141	33,588	138,488	172,076	14,065	182,719
	285,095	365,427	637,387	115,152	474,014	589,166	48,220	626,428
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,189	1,084	-	-	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,007	(383)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	1,500	12,000	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	425	78	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	10,196	12,778	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total indirect costs	3,874	296	-	-	-	-	-	-
	14,070	13,074	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.3 State of the Arctic								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	139,865	182,832	213,925	-	213,925	(31,093)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	3,615	43,388	37,503	-	37,503	5,885	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	72,731	66,825	-	66,825	5,906	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	2,000	5,456	-	5,456	(3,456)	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	225	23,500	23,370	-	23,370	21,130	-
Consulting	-	10,652	25,000	20,206	-	20,206	4,794	-
Computer Services	-	1,523	1,000	172	-	172	828	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	47,557	86,000	124,149	-	124,149	(38,149)	-
Total direct costs	-	203,436	436,451	470,607	-	470,607	(34,156)	-
Total indirect costs	-	73,506	179,731	193,796	-	193,796	(14,065)	-
TOTAL FOR SOA	-	276,942	616,182	664,402	-	664,402	(48,220)	-
Subtotal Direct Community Science Planning	216,768	486,524	887,698	852,171	335,527	887,698	-	443,708
Subtotal Indirect	82,398	168,918	365,872	227,384	138,488	365,872	0	182,719
Total Community Science Planning	299,166	655,442	1,253,569	779,555	474,014	1,253,569	0	626,428
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION								
2.1 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION								
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,245	51,542	19,025	4,017	15,008	19,025	-	28,589
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,851	2,584	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	6,734	2,279	48,317	-	42,417	42,417	5,900	-
Materials and Supplies	69	-	50	-	50	50	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	10	-	-	52	-	52	(52)	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	5,156	1,802	500	412	88	500	-	-
Subawards	101,148	13,598	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,709	1,040	6,850	7	6,843	6,850	-	-
Total direct costs	143,922	72,845	74,742	4,489	64,405	68,894	5,848	28,589
Total indirect costs	16,254	13,394	31,097	1,849	26,840	28,689	2,408	11,773
	160,176	86,238	105,839	6,338	91,245	97,583	8,258	40,361

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.								
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009 - YEAR 2	2010	2010	2010	2010	2010	2011
	TOTAL							
	ACTUAL	ACTUAL	BUDGET	AS OF 06/30/10	JULY-DEC	& FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET
2.2 ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION								
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,632	17,987	23,090	2,023	21,067	23,090	(0)	29,771
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	989	1,109	2,738	1,972	766	2,738	-	2,875
Participant Support Costs	8,429	5,012	21,616	6,987	13,895	20,882	734	20,482
Materials and Supplies	69	-	160	-	160	160	-	100
Publications/Dissemination	10	-	1,000	-	1,000	1,000	-	3,000
Consulting	-	2,000	2,000	-	2,000	2,000	-	-
Computer Services	-	605	-	413	-	413	(413)	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	672	282	100	421	-	421	(321)	100
Total direct costs	12,801	24,995	50,703	11,816	38,887	50,703	(0)	56,328
Total indirect costs	4,864	3,798	20,880	4,866	16,014	20,880	-	23,196
	17,665	28,794	71,583	16,682	54,901	71,583	(0)	79,525
2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION								
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	148	100	248	(248)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	5,000	5,000	(5,000)	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	400	400	(400)	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	200	200	200	(200)	-
Total direct costs	-	-	-	148	5,700	5,848	(5,848)	-
Total indirect costs	-	-	-	61	2,347	2,408	(2,408)	-
	-	-	-	210	8,048	8,258	(8,258)	-
2.4 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS								
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	3,583	50	3,533	3,583	-	7,663
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	400	-	400	400	-	400
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	1,000	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	-	1,000	3,983	50	3,933	3,983	-	8,063
Total indirect costs	-	-	1,640	20	1,620	1,640	0	3,320
	-	1,000	5,623	70	5,553	5,623	0	11,383
Subtotal Direct Costs Arctic Sciences Section	156,723	98,840	129,428	16,503	112,925	129,428	(0)	92,980
Subtotal Indirect Costs	21,117	17,192	53,617	6,797	46,821	53,618	(0)	38,289
Total Arctic Sciences Section	177,840	116,032	183,046	23,301	159,746	183,047	(0)	131,269
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION								
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,790	8,692	15,619	5,739	9,880	15,619	-	29,420
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,763	6,410	3,499	1,363	1,884	3,247	252	5,750
Participant Support Costs	5,556	(168)	1,498	-	1,498	1,498	-	10,241
Materials and Supplies	-	48	150	-	150	150	-	200
Publications/Dissemination	953	-	100	-	100	100	-	150
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	2,002	500	172	328	500	-	500
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,701	293	100	352	-	352	(252)	-
Total direct costs	24,763	17,277	21,466	7,626	13,840	21,466	-	46,261
Total indirect cost	9,410	6,565	8,840	3,140	5,700	8,840	0	19,050
	34,173	23,842	30,306	10,766	19,541	30,306	0	65,312

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.								
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009 - YEAR 2	2010	2010	2010	2010	2010	2011
	year)							
	TOTAL	ACTUAL	BUDGET	AS OF 06/30/10	JULY-DEC	& FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,033	13,973	11,830	3,370	8,460	11,830	-	26,073
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	2,502	1,886	14,800	4,082	10,718	14,800	-	19,400
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	127	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	150	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	792	2,000	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	5,454	18,009	26,630	7,452	19,178	26,630	-	45,473
Total indirect costs	2,073	6,084	11,125	3,068	8,057	11,125	-	18,726
	7,527	24,093	37,757	10,520	27,235	37,757	-	64,199
Subtotal Direct Costs Arctic Science Education	30,217	35,286	48,096	15,078	33,018	48,096	-	91,734
Subtotal Indirect Costs	11,482	12,649	19,966	6,208	13,758	19,965	-	37,777
Total Arctic Science Education	41,699	47,935	68,062	21,286	46,776	68,062	0	129,511
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH								
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	21,506	22,509	35,111	11,618	23,493	35,111	0	88,244
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	100	-	100	100	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	30	37,315	1,200	-	1,200	1,200	-	350
Consulting	15,325	18,350	23,000	2,250	20,750	23,000	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	131	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	36,861	78,305	59,411	13,868	45,543	59,411	0	88,594
Total indirect costs	14,007	29,756	24,466	5,711	18,755	24,466	(0)	36,483
	50,868	108,061	83,877	19,580	64,297	83,877	(0)	125,077
4.2 ARCUS Internet Resources								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	108,889	55,502	91,005	17,013	73,992	91,005	-	113,000
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	85	4,262	3,475	1,851	1,403	3,254	221	2,875
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	92	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	15,000	-	15,000	15,000	-	7,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	5,680	-	221	-	221	(221)	-
Total direct costs	108,974	65,535	109,480	19,085	90,395	109,480	-	122,875
Total indirect costs	41,410	23,003	45,084	7,859	37,225	45,084	-	50,600
	150,384	88,538	154,564	26,944	127,620	154,564	-	173,474
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	14,334	30,906	26,925	10,417	16,508	26,925	0	36,098
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	14,334	30,906	26,925	10,417	16,508	26,925	0	36,098
Total indirect costs	5,447	11,744	11,088	4,290	6,798	11,088	(0)	14,865
	19,781	42,650	38,013	14,707	23,307	38,013	0	50,964

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.								
Budget Explanation	2008 9-month	2009 - YEAR 2	2010	2010	2010	2010	2010	2011
	TOTAL							
	ACTUAL	ACTUAL	BUDGET	AS OF 06/30/10	JULY-DEC	& FORECAST	REMAINING	BUDGET
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,002	6,780	7,995	2,406	5,589	7,995	-	12,859
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	1,002	6,780	7,995	2,406	5,589	7,995	-	12,859
Total indirect costs	381	2,576	3,292	991	2,302	3,292	-	5,296
	1,383	9,356	11,287	3,397	7,890	11,287	-	18,155
4.5 Internet Media Archive								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,037	29,196	38,614	10,638	27,976	38,614	(0)	46,837
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	7,087	29,196	38,614	10,638	27,976	38,614	(0)	46,887
Total indirect costs	2,693	11,095	15,901	4,381	11,520	15,901	0	19,308
	9,780	40,291	54,515	15,019	39,497	54,515	0	66,195
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	83,312	18,082	19,341	1,251	18,090	19,341	-	60,072
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	33,341	8,073	13,688	(974)	14,465	13,491	197	14,375
Participant Support Costs	44,304	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	316	-	200	-	200	200	-	2,000
Publications/Dissemination	13,321	6,247	600	47	509	556	44	600
Consulting	1,250	11,225	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	241	-	241	(241)	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	59,932	18,011	20,000	(69)	20,069	20,000	-	25,000
Total direct costs	235,776	61,637	53,828	496	53,332	53,828	-	102,047
Total indirect costs	89,595	19,242	22,166	203	21,963	22,166	-	42,023
	325,371	80,879	75,994	699	75,295	75,994	-	144,070
Subtotal Direct Information and Outreach	404,034	272,360	296,253	56,910	239,344	296,253	0	409,359
Subtotal Indirect	153,533	97,417	121,996	23,435	98,562	121,996	(0)	168,574
Total Information and Outreach	557,567	369,776	418,249	80,345	337,907	418,249	0	577,932
5. CORE SUPPORT								
5.1 Core Support								
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	108,045	122,518	141,159	45,052	77,516	122,568	18,591	147,479
Permanent Equipment	20,800	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	359	5,725	5,475	5,541	-	5,541	(66)	11,000
Participant Support Costs	-	558	-	2,499	-	2,499	(2,499)	-
Materials and supplies	21,341	12,137	33,000	9,483	23,517	33,000	-	45,500
Publications/Dissemination	1,288	20	500	-	500	500	-	500
Consulting	19,450	5,100	1,000	-	1,000	1,000	-	5,000
Computer Services	42,689	35,295	-	15,718	-	15,718	(15,718)	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	17,581	2,713	500	809	-	809	(309)	1,200
Total direct costs	231,553	184,066	181,635	79,102	102,533	181,635	0	210,679
Total indirect costs	87,990	69,945	74,797	32,574	42,223	74,797	-	86,758
Total Core Support	319,543	254,011	256,433	111,676	144,757	256,433	0	297,436
Total Direct Costs all tasks	1,039,408	1,077,076	1,543,111	719,762	823,350	1,543,111	(0)	1,248,461
Total Indirect Costs all tasks	356,406	366,121	636,249	296,397	339,852	636,249	0	514,116
Total All Tasks	1,395,815	1,443,197	2,179,355	1,016,160	1,163,202	2,179,355	(0)	1,762,579
							Balance YR 3	0
							Year 4 Budget	1,762,579
							FUNDING REQUEST	1,762,579

ATTACHMENT B

SUMMARY OF PROPOSED FUNDING		2008	2009	2010	2010	2011
		Total	Year 2	2010	2010	2011
Form 1030 Category		Actual	Actual	Actual	Year 3	Year 4
		(9 month year)		& forecast	Remaining	Budget
					(over)	
Salaries	President		-	-	-	-
	Executive director	45,805	69,682	118,778	(15,516)	95,790
	Other professionals	231,758	356,293	396,855	(130)	501,547
	Student	34,344	2,623	25,027	0	0
	Clerical	14,084	54,255	48,895	6,407	35,525
	Total salaries	325,992	482,852	589,555	(9,239)	632,862
		0				
Fringe Benefits		130,016	212,927	224,030	(3,511)	259,473
	Total salaries and fringe benefits	456,008	695,779	813,583	(12,750)	892,336
Permanent Equipment		20,800	0	0		0
Travel (domestic)		70,614	53,823	87,866	11,487	54,875
Travel (foreign)		0	0	4,998	(4,998)	5,000
	Total staff travel	70,614	53,823	92,864	6,489	59,875
Participant Support Costs						
	Stipends	400	400	800	5,000	2,400
	Travel	61,607	33,752	117,310	14,984	65,700
	Subsistence	60,483	21,318	183,914	24,213	101,502
	Total participant costs	122,490	55,470	302,024	44,197	169,602
Other Direct Costs						
	Materials and supplies	21,951	12,277	40,216	(3,456)	48,300
	Publication cost/ docum/dissem	18,968	45,007	16,053	16,122	6,550
	Consultant services	40,575	63,027	63,106	4,394	12,000
	Computer services	50,423	43,606	19,544	(15,544)	1,500
	Subawards	101,148	13,598	0	0	0
	Other	136,431	94,490	195,722	(39,452)	58,300
	Total other direct costs	369,496	272,005	334,641	(37,936)	126,650
	Total direct costs	1,039,408	1,077,076	1,543,111	0	1,248,461
Indirect Costs (FY09 provisional 38%)		356,406	366,121	636,249	0	514,116
(FY10 & FY11 AT 41.18%)						
	Total direct and indirect costs	1,395,815	1,443,197	2,179,355	0	1,762,579
				NSF CA-approved		
				NSF supplement	2,026,742	
				Adj to Education	203,747	
				Reprogram to 09	(16,634)	
					(34,500)	
				2010 BUDGET	<u>2,179,355</u>	
ATTACHMENT C						

FOR NSF USE ONLY

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)		PROPOSAL NO.		DURATION (MONTHS)	
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/PROJECT DIRECTOR		AWARD NO.		Proposed	Granted
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PIs, Faculty and Other Senior Associates List each separately with name and title. (A.7. Show number in brackets)		NSF-Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By Proposer	Funds Granted by NSF (If Different)
		CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1. Executive Director – Susan Fox		8			95,790 \$
2. Director of Programs – Helen Wiggins		11			104,186
3.					
4.					
5.					
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET EXPLANATION PAGE)					
7. (2) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1-6)					199,976
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)					
1. () POSTDOCTORAL ASSOCIATES					
2. (10) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)		75			397,361
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS					
4. () UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS					
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)					35,525
6. () OTHER					
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					632,862
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					259,474
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					892,336
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)					
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				54,875	
2. FOREIGN				5,000	
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT					
1. STIPENDS \$ 2,400					
2. TRAVEL 65,700					
3. SUBSISTENCE 101,502					
4. OTHER -0-					
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (54)		TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS		169,602	
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS					
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				48,300	
2. PUBLICATION/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				6,550	
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				12,000	
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				1,500	
5. SUBAWARDS				-0-	
6. OTHER				58,300	
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				126,650	
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				1,248,461	
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A) (SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) 41.18% on H – G5					
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				514,116	
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				1,762,579	
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECT SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)+ Amend #3				-0-	
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				1,762,579 \$	
M. COST SHARING: PROPOSED LEVEL \$		AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT: \$			
PI/PD TYPED NAME AND SIGNATURE*		DATE		FOR NSF USE ONLY	
		10/12/10		INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION	
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*		DATE		Date Checked	Date of Rate Sheet
				Initials-ORG	